

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Estrone

CHID: 22367 CASRN: 53-16-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J11

M4ID: 30005399

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0122 MAX_MED: 0.0299 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Androstene-3,17-dione

CHID: 24523 CASRN: 63-05-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N10

M4ID: 30005304

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00503 MAX_MED: -0.101 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dimethomorph

CHID: 34545 CASRN: 110488-70-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I22

M4ID: 30005412

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0792 MAX_MED: 0.00277 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Tebufenozide

CHID: 34948 CASRN: 112410-23-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C03

M4ID: 30005575

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0389 MAX_MED: -0.0183 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Testosterone propionate

CHID: 36515 CASRN: 57-85-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C07

M4ID: 30005955

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.141 MAX_MED: 0.0663 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: DMSO.POS (spid not in DB)

CHID: NA CASRN: NA

SPID(S): DMSO.POS

M4ID: 30006010

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	NA	NA	NA
PROB:	NA	NA	NA
RMSE:	NA	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.00312 MAX_MED: 0 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: -1 FITC: 2 ACTP: NA

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Acetaminophen

CHID: 20006 CASRN: 103-90-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P21

M4ID: 30005629

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-1.15	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.147 MAX_MED: -0.0912 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Acifluorfen

CHID: 20022 CASRN: 50594-66-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J03

M4ID: 30005407

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.288 MAX_MED: 0.277 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Allantoin

CHID: 20043 CASRN: 97-59-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P11

M4ID: 30005639

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0928 MAX_MED: -0.117 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Aminoanthraquinone
 CHID: 20068 CASRN: 117-79-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D15
 M4ID: 30005923

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-11.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0114 MAX_MED: 0.019 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Amitrole

CHID: 20076 CASRN: 61-82-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078020

M4ID: 30005654

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	6.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.118 MAX_MED: -0.0671 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: (E)-Anethole

CHID: 20087 CASRN: 4180-23-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D05

M4ID: 30005933

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00997 MAX_MED: 0.0971 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Aniline hydrochloride
 CHID: 20091 CASRN: 142-04-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L10
 M4ID: 30005736

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-16.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.191 MAX_MED: 0.223 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Methoxyaniline hydrochloride

CHID: 20093 CASRN: 20265-97-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G07

M4ID: 30005859

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-27.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.218 MAX_MED: 0.26 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Aspartame

CHID: 20107 CASRN: 22839-47-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K12

M4ID: 30005374

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-8.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.12 MAX_MED: 0.18 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Aspirin

CHID: 20108 CASRN: 50-78-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D13

M4ID: 30005925

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	3.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0779 MAX_MED: -0.0748 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Atrazine

CHID: 20112 CASRN: 1912-24-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N11

M4ID: 30005303

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-26.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.301 MAX_MED: 0.301 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Sodium azide

CHID: 20121 CASRN: 26628-22-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D11

M4ID: 30005543

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0427 MAX_MED: 0.0272 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Azobenzene

CHID: 20123 CASRN: 103-33-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C12

M4ID: 30005950

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-10.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0207 MAX_MED: 0.00466 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 3'-Azido-3'-deoxythymidine

CHID: 20127 CASRN: 30516-87-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L14

M4ID: 30005348

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0203 MAX_MED: 0.0639 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Benzidine

CHID: 20137 CASRN: 92-87-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G13

M4ID: 30005853

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.271 MAX_MED: 0.405 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2,3-Benzofuran

CHID: 20141 CASRN: 271-89-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D21

M4ID: 30005533

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-23.07	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.00355 MAX_MED: -0.0081 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Benzoic acid

CHID: 20143 CASRN: 65-85-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G12

M4ID: 30005854

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-42.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0545 MAX_MED: 0.0271 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,2,3-Benzotriazole
 CHID: 20147 CASRN: 95-14-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N21
 M4ID: 30005677

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-18.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0531 MAX_MED: 0.0196 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Benzyl acetate

CHID: 20151 CASRN: 140-11-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D23

M4ID: 30005915

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-9.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0203 MAX_MED: 0.000982 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Benzyl alcohol

CHID: 20152 CASRN: 100-51-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N07

M4ID: 30005691

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-22	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00465 MAX_MED: 0.0376 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Biphenyl

CHID: 20161 CASRN: 92-52-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I06

M4ID: 30005812

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-27.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0366 MAX_MED: 0.0265 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Pentaerythritol dibromide

CHID: 20164 CASRN: 3296-90-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I12

M4ID: 30005806

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-27.89	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0187 MAX_MED: -0.0146 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Bis(2-chloroethyl) ether

CHID: 20168 CASRN: 111-44-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K03

M4ID: 30005767

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-21.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.158 MAX_MED: 0.16 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: C.I. Acid Blue 74

CHID: 20190 CASRN: 860-22-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091019

M4ID: 30005271

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	34.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.119 MAX_MED: 0.00277 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Benzyl butyl phthalate

CHID: 20205 CASRN: 85-68-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P16

M4ID: 30005250

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	27.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.024 MAX_MED: 0.122 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Butylparaben

CHID: 20209 CASRN: 94-26-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B17

M4ID: 30005585

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-8.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0511 MAX_MED: 0.151 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Methyl-2-tert-butylphenol

CHID: 20212 CASRN: 2409-55-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078002

M4ID: 30005672

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	13.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.176 MAX_MED: -0.159 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-tert-Butylphenol

CHID: 20221 CASRN: 98-54-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B22

M4ID: 30005964

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-22.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0364 MAX_MED: 0.00704 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Butyrolactone

CHID: 20224 CASRN: 96-48-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N12

M4ID: 30005302

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.139 MAX_MED: 0.12 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Caffeine

CHID: 20232 CASRN: 58-08-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K18

M4ID: 30005752

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-33.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0609 MAX_MED: 0.0722 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1-Chloro-4-nitrobenzene

CHID: 20281 CASRN: 100-00-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B05

M4ID: 30005981

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-52.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0655 MAX_MED: 0.143 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Chloro-1,2-diaminobenzene

CHID: 20283 CASRN: 95-83-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M06

M4ID: 30005332

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	4.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0957 MAX_MED: 0.0284 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 3-Chloro-4-methylaniline

CHID: 20286 CASRN: 95-74-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F09

M4ID: 30005881

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-30.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0829 MAX_MED: 0.141 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Chloroaniline

CHID: 20295 CASRN: 106-47-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H15

M4ID: 30005443

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.264 MAX_MED: 0.39 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Monuron

CHID: 20311 CASRN: 150-68-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J12

M4ID: 30005782

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-48.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0634 MAX_MED: 0.104 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Citric acid

CHID: 20332 CASRN: 77-92-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H23

M4ID: 30005819

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-17.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.121 MAX_MED: 0.122 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Methoxy-5-methylaniline

CHID: 20350 CASRN: 120-71-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E10

M4ID: 30005520

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	15.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.163 MAX_MED: -0.0666 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Cupferron

CHID: 20352 CASRN: 135-20-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D16

M4ID: 30005922

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	17.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.00698 MAX_MED: -0.0309 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Cyclohexanone

CHID: 20359 CASRN: 108-94-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I17

M4ID: 30005801

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-8.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.229 MAX_MED: 0.282 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dehydroepiandrosterone

CHID: 20379 CASRN: 53-43-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D18

M4ID: 30005536

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	16.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.109 MAX_MED: 0.0278 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dibenz(a,h)anthracene
CHID: 20409 CASRN: 53-70-3
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H04
M4ID: 30005838

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0424 MAX_MED: -0.0553 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Propyzamide

CHID: 20420 CASRN: 23950-58-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K12

M4ID: 30005758

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-29.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.175 MAX_MED: 0.183 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,4-Dichlorobenzene

CHID: 20431 CASRN: 106-46-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091014

M4ID: 30005276

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	31.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0599 MAX_MED: -0.113 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dichlorprop

CHID: 20440 CASRN: 120-36-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B13

M4ID: 30005973

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.89	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00743 MAX_MED: 0.0547 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2,4-D Butyl ester

CHID: 20443 CASRN: 94-80-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H13

M4ID: 30005829

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-3.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00542 MAX_MED: 0.126 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dichlorvos

CHID: 20449 CASRN: 62-73-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D14

M4ID: 30005540

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-21.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0452 MAX_MED: -0.0518 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Diethylene glycol

CHID: 20462 CASRN: 111-46-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F18

M4ID: 30005872

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-10.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0333 MAX_MED: 0.0409 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dimethyl hydrogen phosphite

CHID: 20493 CASRN: 868-85-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J19

M4ID: 30005391

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.172 MAX_MED: 0.0957 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dimethyl methylphosphonate

CHID: 20494 CASRN: 756-79-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M20

M4ID: 30005318

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	30.89	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.169 MAX_MED: 0.124 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dimethylaminoethanol
 CHID: 20505 CASRN: 108-01-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H24
 M4ID: 30005434

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-44.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.149 MAX_MED: 0.117 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: N,N-Dimethylaniline

CHID: 20507 CASRN: 121-69-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E08

M4ID: 30005906

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	3.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0559 MAX_MED: -0.0751 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,1-Dimethylhydrazine
 CHID: 20516 CASRN: 57-14-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H06
 M4ID: 30005836

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-4.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 7.35e-05 MAX_MED: -0.0283 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2,6-Dinitrotoluene

CHID: 20528 CASRN: 606-20-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J06

M4ID: 30005788

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-6.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.021 MAX_MED: 0.0482 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2,4-Dinitrotoluene

CHID: 20529 CASRN: 121-14-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L02

M4ID: 30005360

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.144 MAX_MED: 0.0909 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Endosulfan

CHID: 20560 CASRN: 115-29-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G03

M4ID: 30005479

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-9.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.208 MAX_MED: 0.189 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Endrin

CHID: 20561 CASRN: 72-20-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F15

M4ID: 30005491

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-12.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0994 MAX_MED: 0.066 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Sodium erythorbate (1:1)

CHID: 20570 CASRN: 6381-77-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H14

M4ID: 30005444

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0304 MAX_MED: -0.0219 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Ethoxyquin

CHID: 20582 CASRN: 91-53-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G19

M4ID: 30005847

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.361 MAX_MED: 0.364 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Ethylene glycol

CHID: 20597 CASRN: 107-21-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D22

M4ID: 30005916

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-21.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0252 MAX_MED: 0.0319 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Vinyl-1-cyclohexene dioxide

CHID: 20604 CASRN: 106-87-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078006

M4ID: 30005668

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	15.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.127 MAX_MED: -0.0534 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Ethyl-1-hexanol

CHID: 20605 CASRN: 104-76-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078021

M4ID: 30005653

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0229 MAX_MED: 0.00911 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Eugeno^l

CHID: 20617 CASRN: 97-53-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K17

M4ID: 30005753

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-6.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.29 MAX_MED: 0.361 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Finasteride

CHID: 20625 CASRN: 98319-26-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D22

M4ID: 30005532

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	17	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0619 MAX_MED: -0.0334 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Fluometuron

CHID: 20628 CASRN: 2164-17-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078012

M4ID: 30005662

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0361 MAX_MED: -0.0628 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 5-Fluorouracil

CHID: 20634 CASRN: 51-21-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I02

M4ID: 30005432

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	3.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0578 MAX_MED: 0.102 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Glycerol

CHID: 20663 CASRN: 56-81-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C17

M4ID: 30005945

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-30.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.162 MAX_MED: 0.142 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 3-Chloro-1,2-propanediol

CHID: 20664 CASRN: 96-24-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I09

M4ID: 30005425

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-7.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.14 MAX_MED: 0.124 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Glycidol

CHID: 20666 CASRN: 556-52-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N20

M4ID: 30005678

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-11.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.107 MAX_MED: 0.0789 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Hexachloro-1,3-butadiene

CHID: 20683 CASRN: 87-68-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I18

M4ID: 30005800

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-10.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.00792 MAX_MED: -0.0373 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: beta-Hexachlorocyclohexane

CHID: 20685 CASRN: 319-85-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H10

M4ID: 30005448

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0439 MAX_MED: 0.00972 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Hexachlorocyclopentadiene

CHID: 20688 CASRN: 77-47-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F06

M4ID: 30005500

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0378 MAX_MED: -0.00708 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Methenamine

CHID: 20692 CASRN: 100-97-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G08

M4ID: 30005474

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-16.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0359 MAX_MED: -0.0728 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,2-Diphenylhydrazine

CHID: 20710 CASRN: 122-66-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C15

M4ID: 30005563

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.09	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.168 MAX_MED: 0.0761 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 8-Hydroxyquinoline

CHID: 20730 CASRN: 148-24-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N06

M4ID: 30005308

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.413 MAX_MED: 0.33 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Isophorone

CHID: 20759 CASRN: 78-59-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L05

M4ID: 30005741

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-40.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0778 MAX_MED: 0.0695 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Maleic hydrazide

CHID: 20792 CASRN: 123-33-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C04

M4ID: 30005574

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.156 MAX_MED: -0.122 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: dl-Menthol

CHID: 20805 CASRN: 89-78-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I14

M4ID: 30005804

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	16.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0206 MAX_MED: 0.101 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Methyl methanesulfonate

CHID: 20845 CASRN: 66-27-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N15

M4ID: 30005299

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	25.41	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.193 MAX_MED: 0.148 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: N-Methyl-2-pyrrolidone
 CHID: 20856 CASRN: 872-50-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A23
 M4ID: 30005987

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-1.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0657 MAX_MED: 0.161 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 6-Methylquinoline

CHID: 20887 CASRN: 91-62-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C06

M4ID: 30005956

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0849 MAX_MED: 0.208 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 6-Methyl-2-thiouracil
 CHID: 20890 CASRN: 56-04-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F19
 M4ID: 30005871

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-18.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.178 MAX_MED: 0.21 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Busulfan

CHID: 20910 CASRN: 55-98-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P15

M4ID: 30005251

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	27.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0224 MAX_MED: -0.108 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Naphthalene

CHID: 20913 CASRN: 91-20-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M02

M4ID: 30005336

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0415 MAX_MED: 0.0546 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1-Naphthaleneacetic acid

CHID: 20915 CASRN: 86-87-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F05

M4ID: 30005501

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-22.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.088 MAX_MED: 0.0611 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Naphthylamine

CHID: 20921 CASRN: 91-59-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G06

M4ID: 30005860

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.103 MAX_MED: -0.0763 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Nicotine

CHID: 20930 CASRN: 54-11-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D07

M4ID: 30005931

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-45.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0886 MAX_MED: 0.0969 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Nicotinic acid

CHID: 20932 CASRN: 59-67-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J10

M4ID: 30005784

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-1.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.215 MAX_MED: 0.207 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Nitriлотriacetic acid
 CHID: 20939 CASRN: 139-13-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A22
 M4ID: 30005988

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0473 MAX_MED: -0.0699 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Methyl-5-nitroaniline

CHID: 20959 CASRN: 99-55-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G18

M4ID: 30005464

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-36.77	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.15 MAX_MED: 0.0982 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Nitrobenzene

CHID: 20964 CASRN: 98-95-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E23

M4ID: 30005507

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-7.84	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.377 MAX_MED: 0.351 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Nitrobenzoic acid

CHID: 20966 CASRN: 62-23-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I03

M4ID: 30005431

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	4.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.25 MAX_MED: 0.342 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Nitrofen

CHID: 20970 CASRN: 1836-75-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N22

M4ID: 30005292

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	42.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.37 MAX_MED: 0.316 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: N-Nitrosodibutylamine
 CHID: 21026 CASRN: 924-16-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J15
 M4ID: 30005395

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.335 MAX_MED: 0.36 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: N-Nitrosodimethylamine

CHID: 21029 CASRN: 62-75-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P13

M4ID: 30005637

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	23.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.185 MAX_MED: -0.234 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: N-Nitrosodipropylamine
 CHID: 21032 CASRN: 621-64-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J14
 M4ID: 30005396

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0874 MAX_MED: 0.0295 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Oxazepam

CHID: 21087 CASRN: 604-75-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A15

M4ID: 30005995

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.137 MAX_MED: 0.105 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4,4'-Oxydianiline

CHID: 21094 CASRN: 101-80-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G10

M4ID: 30005856

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.052 MAX_MED: 0.0295 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Oxytetracycline hydrochloride

CHID: 21097 CASRN: 2058-46-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P02

M4ID: 30005264

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-6.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.346 MAX_MED: 0.355 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Phenothiazine

CHID: 21126 CASRN: 92-84-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D19

M4ID: 30005919

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-6.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.262 MAX_MED: 0.24 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,3-Benzenediamine

CHID: 21137 CASRN: 108-45-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A21

M4ID: 30005989

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-24.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0551 MAX_MED: 0.0755 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Phenylphenol

CHID: 21151 CASRN: 90-43-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N03

M4ID: 30005311

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	23.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.33	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.285 MAX_MED: 0.215 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Picloram

CHID: 21160 CASRN: 1918-02-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K18

M4ID: 30005368

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.19 MAX_MED: 0.199 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Prednisone

CHID: 21185 CASRN: 53-03-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I05

M4ID: 30005813

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-21.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.017 MAX_MED: -0.0343 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Propazine

CHID: 21196 CASRN: 139-40-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E18

M4ID: 30005512

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	19.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.205 MAX_MED: -0.124 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Pebulate

CHID: 21199 CASRN: 1114-71-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H11

M4ID: 30005831

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-28.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.247 MAX_MED: 0.253 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 6-Propyl-2-thiouracil

CHID: 21209 CASRN: 51-52-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A20

M4ID: 30005990

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.04 MAX_MED: -0.0413 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Sodium chlorite

CHID: 21272 CASRN: 7758-19-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J11

M4ID: 30005783

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-16.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.235 MAX_MED: 0.259 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2E,4E-Hexadienoic acid
 CHID: 21277 CASRN: 110-44-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K24
 M4ID: 30005746

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-32.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.172 MAX_MED: 0.17 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Disulfiram

CHID: 21322 CASRN: 97-77-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G21

M4ID: 30005845

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-10.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.259 MAX_MED: 0.351 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Thiabendazole

CHID: 21337 CASRN: 148-79-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A05

M4ID: 30005621

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.313 MAX_MED: 0.304 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Thiourea

CHID: 21348 CASRN: 62-56-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L17

M4ID: 30005345

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.291 MAX_MED: 0.246 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: dl- α -Tocopheryl acetate

CHID: 21356 CASRN: 52225-20-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D08

M4ID: 30005930

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.1 MAX_MED: -0.0882 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2,4,6-Trichlorophenol
 CHID: 21386 CASRN: 88-06-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F06
 M4ID: 30005884

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.197 MAX_MED: 0.247 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Triethylene glycol

CHID: 21393 CASRN: 112-27-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078017

M4ID: 30005657

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-18.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0814 MAX_MED: 0.0377 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Trifluralin

CHID: 21395 CASRN: 1582-09-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B08

M4ID: 30005594

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.09	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0778 MAX_MED: 0.00669 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,2,4-Trimethylbenzene

CHID: 21402 CASRN: 95-63-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I08

M4ID: 30005426

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0956 MAX_MED: 0.0911 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Trimethyl phosphate

CHID: 21403 CASRN: 512-56-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F18

M4ID: 30005488

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0188 MAX_MED: 0.0247 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Urethane

CHID: 21427 CASRN: 51-79-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M11

M4ID: 30005327

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.367 MAX_MED: 0.367 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Fumaric acid

CHID: 21518 CASRN: 110-17-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P23

M4ID: 30005627

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	23.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.211 MAX_MED: -0.156 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-(2-Butoxyethoxy)ethanol

CHID: 21519 CASRN: 112-34-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N17

M4ID: 30005681

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-26.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0795 MAX_MED: 0.158 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-[2-(2-Butoxyethoxy)ethoxy]ethanol

CHID: 21520 CASRN: 143-22-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F16

M4ID: 30005874

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	24.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.114 MAX_MED: -0.0415 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Decanal

CHID: 21553 CASRN: 112-31-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E24

M4ID: 30005890

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.116 MAX_MED: -0.042 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Decanoic acid

CHID: 21554 CASRN: 334-48-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D21

M4ID: 30005917

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-34.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0884 MAX_MED: 0.0938 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dalapon

CHID: 21575 CASRN: 75-99-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P22

M4ID: 30005628

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.114 MAX_MED: -0.124 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Heptanoic acid

CHID: 21600 CASRN: 111-14-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P03

M4ID: 30005263

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12.22	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0192 MAX_MED: -0.029 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Hexanoic acid

CHID: 21607 CASRN: 142-62-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N06

M4ID: 30005692

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00959 MAX_MED: -0.0224 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Nonanoic acid

CHID: 21641 CASRN: 112-05-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M21

M4ID: 30005701

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-20.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.151 MAX_MED: 0.208 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Octanal

CHID: 21643 CASRN: 124-13-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E18

M4ID: 30005896

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.122 MAX_MED: -0.0986 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Octanoic acid

CHID: 21645 CASRN: 124-07-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P07

M4ID: 30005643

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0696 MAX_MED: -0.0563 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Tetradecanoic acid

CHID: 21666 CASRN: 544-63-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L23

M4ID: 30005723

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.219 MAX_MED: 0.224 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dimethyl sulfoxide

CHID: 21735 CASRN: 67-68-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B11

M4ID: 30005591

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-11.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.12 MAX_MED: 0.104 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1-Propanol

CHID: 21739 CASRN: 71-23-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N24

M4ID: 30005674

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	3.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.037 MAX_MED: 0.125 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 5,5-Dimethylhydantoin
 CHID: 21754 CASRN: 77-71-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J07
 M4ID: 30005787

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-21.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.169 MAX_MED: 0.146 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Tris(2-butoxyethyl) phosphate

CHID: 21758 CASRN: 78-51-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078022

M4ID: 30005652

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.065 MAX_MED: 0.122 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-(2-Methylbutan-2-yl)phenol

CHID: 21771 CASRN: 80-46-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A18

M4ID: 30005992

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.75	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0468 MAX_MED: 0.044 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Diethyl phthalate

CHID: 21780 CASRN: 84-66-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J16

M4ID: 30005394

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.121 MAX_MED: 0.0789 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1-Naphthol

CHID: 21793 CASRN: 90-15-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F01

M4ID: 30005505

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-27.41	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.116 MAX_MED: 0.0305 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Quinoline

CHID: 21798 CASRN: 91-22-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I10

M4ID: 30005424

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0205 MAX_MED: 0.0985 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: N,N-Diethylaniline

CHID: 21800 CASRN: 91-66-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N02

M4ID: 30005312

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.102 MAX_MED: 0.0452 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: o-Cresol

CHID: 21808 CASRN: 95-48-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N23

M4ID: 30005675

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-25.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0548 MAX_MED: 0.0995 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Butanone oxime

CHID: 21821 CASRN: 96-29-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H21

M4ID: 30005437

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.21 MAX_MED: 0.205 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Acetophenone

CHID: 21828 CASRN: 98-86-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H08

M4ID: 30005834

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-6.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0106 MAX_MED: -0.00383 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 3-Nitrotoluene

CHID: 21831 CASRN: 99-08-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B16

M4ID: 30005586

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0538 MAX_MED: -0.0681 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: N,N,4-Trimethylaniline

CHID: 21832 CASRN: 99-97-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078018

M4ID: 30005656

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-3.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0536 MAX_MED: -0.112 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Cyclohexanone oxime
 CHID: 21842 CASRN: 100-64-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M10
 M4ID: 30005328

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	22.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0712 MAX_MED: 0.0866 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: N-Ethyl-3-methylaniline

CHID: 21848 CASRN: 102-27-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N18

M4ID: 30005680

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-12.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0357 MAX_MED: 0.061 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2,4-Dimethylphenol

CHID: 21864 CASRN: 105-67-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M08

M4ID: 30005330

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	16.09	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.199 MAX_MED: 0.0633 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: p-Cresol

CHID: 21869 CASRN: 106-44-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A07

M4ID: 30006003

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-24.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.352 MAX_MED: 0.349 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Methyl-2,4-pentanediol

CHID: 21885 CASRN: 107-41-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H07

M4ID: 30005835

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-35.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.161 MAX_MED: 0.186 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Pentanone

CHID: 21888 CASRN: 107-87-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P12

M4ID: 30005254

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	19.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0976 MAX_MED: -0.0631 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Cyclohexanol

CHID: 21894 CASRN: 108-93-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F17

M4ID: 30005873

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.151 MAX_MED: 0.0928 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Propanedinitrile

CHID: 21907 CASRN: 109-77-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F19

M4ID: 30005487

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-16.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.136 MAX_MED: 0.123 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 5-Methyl-2-hexanone

CHID: 21914 CASRN: 110-12-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K20

M4ID: 30005366

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	23.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.221 MAX_MED: 0.196 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-(Ethylamino)ethanol

CHID: 21922 CASRN: 110-73-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G04

M4ID: 30005862

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0935 MAX_MED: -0.0493 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Ethylene glycol monoethyl ether acetate

CHID: 21928 CASRN: 111-15-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J20

M4ID: 30005774

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-38.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0703 MAX_MED: 0.118 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Hexanedinitrile

CHID: 21936 CASRN: 111-69-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M14

M4ID: 30005324

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	23.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0151 MAX_MED: -0.0586 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1-Octanol

CHID: 21940 CASRN: 111-87-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F21

M4ID: 30005869

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-28.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.121 MAX_MED: 0.106 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-(2-Ethoxyethoxy)ethanol

CHID: 21941 CASRN: 111-90-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G18

M4ID: 30005848

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-8.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0338 MAX_MED: 0.0192 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Undecanone

CHID: 21943 CASRN: 112-12-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L07

M4ID: 30005739

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-23.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.18 MAX_MED: 0.242 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1-Decanol

CHID: 21946 CASRN: 112-30-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I22

M4ID: 30005796

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-20.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.133 MAX_MED: 0.101 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Propoxur

CHID: 21948 CASRN: 114-26-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F08

M4ID: 30005498

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0621 MAX_MED: 0.0593 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Benzophenone

CHID: 21961 CASRN: 119-61-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D18

M4ID: 30005920

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-22.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0433 MAX_MED: 0.0129 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde

CHID: 21969 CASRN: 121-33-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M24

M4ID: 30005698

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-9.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.183 MAX_MED: 0.23 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Diphenylamine

CHID: 21975 CASRN: 122-39-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J18

M4ID: 30005776

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.1 MAX_MED: 0.0739 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Phenoxyethanol

CHID: 21976 CASRN: 122-99-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C22

M4ID: 30005940

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-16.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00623 MAX_MED: 0.0799 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Ethyl hexanoate

CHID: 21980 CASRN: 123-66-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M03

M4ID: 30005719

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-1.09	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.156 MAX_MED: 0.172 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Tributyl phosphate

CHID: 21986 CASRN: 126-73-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K01

M4ID: 30005385

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.336 MAX_MED: 0.4 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dibenzofuran

CHID: 21993 CASRN: 132-64-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P14

M4ID: 30005252

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	28.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0598 MAX_MED: -0.216 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: DEET

CHID: 21995 CASRN: 134-62-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A08

M4ID: 30005618

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	27.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.215 MAX_MED: -0.129 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Ethanolamine

CHID: 22000 CASRN: 141-43-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H21

M4ID: 30005821

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-21.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.151 MAX_MED: 0.216 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1-Nonanol

CHID: 22008 CASRN: 143-08-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M22

M4ID: 30005700

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-22.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0318 MAX_MED: 0.0174 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Disulfoton

CHID: 22018 CASRN: 298-04-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B23

M4ID: 30005579

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-9.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0571 MAX_MED: 0.0691 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Bromacil

CHID: 22020 CASRN: 314-40-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G10

M4ID: 30005472

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-11.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0503 MAX_MED: -0.0357 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Flavone

CHID: 22048 CASRN: 525-82-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G11

M4ID: 30005471

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-17.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.131 MAX_MED: 0.143 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,3-Dichlorobenzene

CHID: 22056 CASRN: 541-73-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C22

M4ID: 30005556

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.127 MAX_MED: -0.146 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: gamma-Decanolactone

CHID: 22109 CASRN: 706-14-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D17

M4ID: 30005921

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-31.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0327 MAX_MED: 0.0571 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 3,4-Dichloro-1-butene
 CHID: 22113 CASRN: 760-23-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H24
 M4ID: 30005818

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.00416 MAX_MED: 0.0143 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: (Z)-3-Hexen-1-ol

CHID: 22137 CASRN: 928-96-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M18

M4ID: 30005704

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0842 MAX_MED: 0.0976 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Resmethrin

CHID: 22253 CASRN: 10453-86-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H03

M4ID: 30005455

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-9.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.209 MAX_MED: 0.287 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Hexyloxyaniline

CHID: 22288 CASRN: 39905-57-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P02

M4ID: 30005648

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	16.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.17 MAX_MED: -0.169 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Triphenylethylene

CHID: 22320 CASRN: 58-72-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K06

M4ID: 30005380

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.138 MAX_MED: 0.113 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2,2-Bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)-1,1,1-trichloroethane

CHID: 22325 CASRN: 2971-36-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B06

M4ID: 30005596

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.256 MAX_MED: 0.296 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-(Butan-2-yl)phenol

CHID: 22331 CASRN: 89-72-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K15

M4ID: 30005371

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.428 MAX_MED: 0.262 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Progesterone

CHID: 22370 CASRN: 57-83-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M06

M4ID: 30005716

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-9.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.284 MAX_MED: 0.313 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 17alpha-Estradiol

CHID: 22377 CASRN: 57-91-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K06

M4ID: 30005764

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0892 MAX_MED: 0.16 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2,4-Dihydroxybenzophenone

CHID: 22406 CASRN: 131-56-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D24

M4ID: 30005530

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-3.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0846 MAX_MED: -0.0726 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Phenol red

CHID: 22408 CASRN: 143-74-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A06

M4ID: 30005620

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.477 MAX_MED: 0.419 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4,4'-Methylenebis(2,6-di-t-butylphenol)

CHID: 22411 CASRN: 118-82-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I02

M4ID: 30005816

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-11.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0109 MAX_MED: -0.0348 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Melatonin

CHID: 22421 CASRN: 73-31-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E07

M4ID: 30005907

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.15	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.198 MAX_MED: 0.186 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4,4'-Diaminobiphenyl methane

CHID: 22422 CASRN: 101-77-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P18

M4ID: 30005632

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.083 MAX_MED: -0.0911 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Diphenolic acid

CHID: 22436 CASRN: 126-00-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L13

M4ID: 30005349

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.162 MAX_MED: 0.102 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Phenolphthalin

CHID: 22439 CASRN: 81-90-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N05

M4ID: 30005309

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.218 MAX_MED: 0.234 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Butylbenzene

CHID: 22472 CASRN: 104-51-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C21

M4ID: 30005557

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.231 MAX_MED: 0.193 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Corticosterone

CHID: 22474 CASRN: 50-22-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091005

M4ID: 30005285

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-9.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.202 MAX_MED: 0.195 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: E-Cinnamic acid

CHID: 22489 CASRN: 140-10-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B01

M4ID: 30005985

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-25.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0183 MAX_MED: 0.0202 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Ethylhexylparaben

CHID: 22525 CASRN: 5153-25-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L11

M4ID: 30005735

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.271 MAX_MED: 0.278 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Lactose

CHID: 23193 CASRN: 63-42-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M01

M4ID: 30005721

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.198 MAX_MED: 0.211 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Mifepristone

CHID: 23322 CASRN: 84371-65-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B01

M4ID: 30005601

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-33.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0456 MAX_MED: 0.118 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Pentaerythritol tetranitrate

CHID: 23430 CASRN: 78-11-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F02

M4ID: 30005504

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-6.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00169 MAX_MED: 0.0145 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Pyridoxine

CHID: 23541 CASRN: 65-23-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G01

M4ID: 30005481

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-18.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0922 MAX_MED: 0.115 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Butanedioic acid

CHID: 23602 CASRN: 110-15-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I07

M4ID: 30005427

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.343 MAX_MED: 0.396 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 6-Thioguanine

CHID: 23652 CASRN: 154-42-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E05

M4ID: 30005909

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-8.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.319 MAX_MED: 0.339 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Tromethamine

CHID: 23723 CASRN: 77-86-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M15

M4ID: 30005707

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	20.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0365 MAX_MED: -0.034 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Warfarin

CHID: 23742 CASRN: 81-81-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B07

M4ID: 30005979

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-28.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.212 MAX_MED: 0.248 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: D-Xylose

CHID: 23745 CASRN: 58-86-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J12

M4ID: 30005398

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.157 MAX_MED: 0.186 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Nitrotoluene

CHID: 23792 CASRN: 99-99-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D06

M4ID: 30005932

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-21.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0522 MAX_MED: 0.151 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Isophorone diisocyanate

CHID: 23826 CASRN: 4098-71-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B08

M4ID: 30005978

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	4.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0177 MAX_MED: 0.0365 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Acenaphthylene

CHID: 23845 CASRN: 208-96-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A06

M4ID: 30006004

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0195 MAX_MED: 0.071 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Acephate

CHID: 23846 CASRN: 30560-19-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C19

M4ID: 30005943

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-21.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.301 MAX_MED: 0.264 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Aldoxycarb

CHID: 23862 CASRN: 1646-88-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078001

M4ID: 30005673

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-12.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.37 MAX_MED: 0.363 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Amitraz

CHID: 23871 CASRN: 33089-61-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D08

M4ID: 30005546

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0258 MAX_MED: -0.0507 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Anisidine

CHID: 23877 CASRN: 90-04-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I10

M4ID: 30005808

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-29.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.000763 MAX_MED: 0.0128 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Clofentezine

CHID: 23881 CASRN: 74115-24-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M05

M4ID: 30005333

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.188 MAX_MED: 0.186 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Asulam

CHID: 23890 CASRN: 3337-71-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F10

M4ID: 30005880

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	13.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0256 MAX_MED: 0.0201 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Benfluralin

CHID: 23899 CASRN: 1861-40-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L04

M4ID: 30005358

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	29.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.106 MAX_MED: 0.106 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Bentazone

CHID: 23901 CASRN: 25057-89-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F04

M4ID: 30005502

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	14.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0853 MAX_MED: -0.145 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Benz(a)anthracene

CHID: 23902 CASRN: 56-55-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K02

M4ID: 30005384

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	6.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0729 MAX_MED: 0.0983 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Butylate

CHID: 23936 CASRN: 2008-41-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B05

M4ID: 30005597

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-41.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.131 MAX_MED: 0.082 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Carbosulfan

CHID: 23950 CASRN: 55285-14-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A15

M4ID: 30005611

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-22.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.2 MAX_MED: 0.163 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Carboxin

CHID: 23951 CASRN: 5234-68-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C16

M4ID: 30005562

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0721 MAX_MED: -0.0451 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Cyclohexylamine

CHID: 23996 CASRN: 108-91-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F08

M4ID: 30005882

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.026 MAX_MED: -0.0179 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Cypermethrin

CHID: 23998 CASRN: 52315-07-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N09

M4ID: 30005689

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-8.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0709 MAX_MED: 0.133 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Diethyl sulfate

CHID: 24045 CASRN: 64-67-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M20

M4ID: 30005702

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0816 MAX_MED: 0.0325 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Diisopropyl methylphosphonate

CHID: 24051 CASRN: 1445-75-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091015

M4ID: 30005275

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	15.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.194 MAX_MED: 0.16 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dimethyl sulfate

CHID: 24055 CASRN: 77-78-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D03

M4ID: 30005551

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-11.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00691 MAX_MED: 0.0246 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dimethylamine

CHID: 24057 CASRN: 124-40-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J05

M4ID: 30005405

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-20.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.172 MAX_MED: 0.153 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 3,3'-Dimethylbenzidine

CHID: 24059 CASRN: 119-93-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G09

M4ID: 30005473

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-10.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.193 MAX_MED: 0.229 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 3,4-Dimethylphenol

CHID: 24062 CASRN: 95-65-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E15

M4ID: 30005515

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0255 MAX_MED: -0.0339 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2,6-Dimethylphenol

CHID: 24063 CASRN: 576-26-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A19

M4ID: 30005991

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.197 MAX_MED: 0.131 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,3-Dinitrobenzene

CHID: 24065 CASRN: 99-65-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N14

M4ID: 30005300

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	38.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.42	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.223 MAX_MED: 0.0316 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Ethion

CHID: 24086 CASRN: 563-12-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E19

M4ID: 30005895

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-9.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.285 MAX_MED: 0.35 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Butoxyethanol

CHID: 24097 CASRN: 111-76-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M12

M4ID: 30005710

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-25.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0731 MAX_MED: 0.0555 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Fenamiphos

CHID: 24102 CASRN: 22224-92-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C08

M4ID: 30005570

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.122 MAX_MED: 0.113 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Flutolanil

CHID: 24109 CASRN: 66332-96-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G17

M4ID: 30005465

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-47.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.139 MAX_MED: 0.156 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Fomesafen

CHID: 24112 CASRN: 72178-02-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A16

M4ID: 30005610

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	6.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0926 MAX_MED: -0.0561 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Isopropalin

CHID: 24157 CASRN: 33820-53-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N12

M4ID: 30005686

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.000947 MAX_MED: 0.0128 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Lactofen

CHID: 24160 CASRN: 77501-63-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I01

M4ID: 30005433

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.185 MAX_MED: 0.229 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Methacrylonitrile

CHID: 24176 CASRN: 126-98-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C20

M4ID: 30005558

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.125 MAX_MED: -0.136 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: MCPB

CHID: 24193 CASRN: 94-81-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K13

M4ID: 30005373

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.346 MAX_MED: 0.26 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Mecoprop

CHID: 24194 CASRN: 93-65-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P03

M4ID: 30005647

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.138 MAX_MED: -0.141 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: m-Cresol

CHID: 24200 CASRN: 108-39-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I19

M4ID: 30005415

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	15.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.294 MAX_MED: 0.255 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Molinate

CHID: 24206 CASRN: 2212-67-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I13

M4ID: 30005805

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.317 MAX_MED: 0.288 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Nitrapyrin

CHID: 24216 CASRN: 1929-82-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G04

M4ID: 30005478

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.000906 MAX_MED: 0.00706 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Oxyfluorfen

CHID: 24241 CASRN: 42874-03-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L08

M4ID: 30005354

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-1.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.294 MAX_MED: 0.199 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Phosphoric acid

CHID: 24263 CASRN: 7664-38-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K14

M4ID: 30005372

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0907 MAX_MED: 0.0589 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Prometryn

CHID: 24272 CASRN: 7287-19-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G16

M4ID: 30005466

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-12.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.02 MAX_MED: 0.0543 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Hexythiazox

CHID: 24299 CASRN: 78587-05-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I24

M4ID: 30005410

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-16.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.183 MAX_MED: 0.232 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Sethoxydim

CHID: 24304 CASRN: 74051-80-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D09

M4ID: 30005545

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0209 MAX_MED: -0.00706 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Sodium fluoroacetate

CHID: 24311 CASRN: 62-74-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N13

M4ID: 30005685

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0604 MAX_MED: -0.155 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Myclobutanil

CHID: 24315 CASRN: 88671-89-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G24

M4ID: 30005842

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-7.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0299 MAX_MED: 0.0529 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Tebuthiuron

CHID: 24316 CASRN: 34014-18-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M04

M4ID: 30005334

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	29.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.148 MAX_MED: 0.254 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Terbacil

CHID: 24317 CASRN: 5902-51-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K05

M4ID: 30005765

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-30.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.307 MAX_MED: 0.308 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,2,4,5-Tetrachlorobenzene

CHID: 24320 CASRN: 95-94-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C24

M4ID: 30005554

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.154 MAX_MED: -0.0812 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Tri-allate

CHID: 24344 CASRN: 2303-17-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K16

M4ID: 30005370

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	15.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.25 MAX_MED: 0.157 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-[2-(2-Ethoxyethoxy)ethoxy]ethanol

CHID: 24368 CASRN: 112-50-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J02

M4ID: 30005408

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.4	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.134 MAX_MED: 0.188 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Acetic acid

CHID: 24394 CASRN: 64-19-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078023

M4ID: 30005651

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-16.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.153 MAX_MED: 0.186 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Aminobenzoic acid
 CHID: 24466 CASRN: 150-13-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C13
 M4ID: 30005949

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-4.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.203 MAX_MED: 0.197 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 5-Amino-2-methylphenol

CHID: 24489 CASRN: 2835-95-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N10

M4ID: 30005688

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.239 MAX_MED: 0.124 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Benzothiazole

CHID: 24586 CASRN: 95-16-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A02

M4ID: 30006008

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	16.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0725 MAX_MED: -0.0821 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Benzyl salicylate

CHID: 24598 CASRN: 118-58-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F07

M4ID: 30005883

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-35.15	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0774 MAX_MED: 0.168 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Diethylene glycol dimethyl ether

CHID: 24621 CASRN: 111-96-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G03

M4ID: 30005863

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.144 MAX_MED: 0.179 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 3-Bromo-1-propanol

CHID: 24657 CASRN: 627-18-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E05

M4ID: 30005525

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1.53	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.219 MAX_MED: 0.234 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Butanal oxime

CHID: 24664 CASRN: 110-69-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A12

M4ID: 30005998

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0549 MAX_MED: -0.0787 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: tert-Butylamine

CHID: 24681 CASRN: 75-64-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P18

M4ID: 30005248

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	3.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0071 MAX_MED: 0.103 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Butyl glycidyl ether

CHID: 24691 CASRN: 2426-08-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B09

M4ID: 30005593

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-23.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0287 MAX_MED: 0.0692 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: D-Camphor

CHID: 24721 CASRN: 464-49-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G14

M4ID: 30005852

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	16.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.161 MAX_MED: -0.137 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Carbendazim

CHID: 24729 CASRN: 10605-21-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P06

M4ID: 30005260

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	4.63	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0776 MAX_MED: -0.068 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,6-Hexanediamine

CHID: 24922 CASRN: 124-09-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L20

M4ID: 30005342

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	18.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.162 MAX_MED: 0.156 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 3,4-Diaminotoluene

CHID: 24930 CASRN: 496-72-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M03

M4ID: 30005335

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	24.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.33	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.279 MAX_MED: 0.322 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Di-tert-butyl peroxide
 CHID: 24955 CASRN: 110-05-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F23
 M4ID: 30005483

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-28.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.148 MAX_MED: 0.114 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4,4'-Dichlorodiphenyl sulfone

CHID: 24986 CASRN: 80-07-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B22

M4ID: 30005580

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	4.15	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0792 MAX_MED: 0.18 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Troclosesene

CHID: 24993 CASRN: 2782-57-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A19

M4ID: 30005607

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0541 MAX_MED: 0.019 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Benzal chloride

CHID: 25014 CASRN: 98-87-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D05

M4ID: 30005549

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-42.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.119 MAX_MED: 0.0772 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dicyclopentadiene

CHID: 25023 CASRN: 77-73-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E04

M4ID: 30005910

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	15.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.132 MAX_MED: -0.138 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Diethylene glycol monomethyl ether

CHID: 25049 CASRN: 111-77-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I24

M4ID: 30005794

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-40.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0749 MAX_MED: 0.08 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Diethylenetriamine

CHID: 25050 CASRN: 111-40-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N03

M4ID: 30005695

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00557 MAX_MED: -0.0482 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dihexyl phthalate

CHID: 25068 CASRN: 84-75-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H12

M4ID: 30005830

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-10.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0301 MAX_MED: 0.00544 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Diisobutyl ketone

CHID: 25080 CASRN: 108-83-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D12

M4ID: 30005926

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	4.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.121 MAX_MED: -0.154 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dimethyl adipate

CHID: 25096 CASRN: 627-93-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K16

M4ID: 30005754

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	27.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.177 MAX_MED: -0.149 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 3-(Dimethylamino)propylamine

CHID: 25102 CASRN: 109-55-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K01

M4ID: 30005769

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-30.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.272 MAX_MED: 0.287 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dimethyl glutarate

CHID: 25122 CASRN: 1119-40-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J22

M4ID: 30005772

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-33.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.166 MAX_MED: 0.157 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,2-Dimethyl-3-nitrobenzene

CHID: 25132 CASRN: 83-41-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L01

M4ID: 30005361

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.201 MAX_MED: 0.182 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,3-Dimethylolurea

CHID: 25141 CASRN: 140-95-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M12

M4ID: 30005326

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-24.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.144 MAX_MED: 0.0643 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Divinylbenzene

CHID: 25216 CASRN: 1321-74-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K04

M4ID: 30005766

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	4.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.154 MAX_MED: -0.126 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: (2-Dodecenyl)succinic anhydride

CHID: 25217 CASRN: 19780-11-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J02

M4ID: 30005792

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0644 MAX_MED: -0.0273 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Ethylhexanoic acid

CHID: 25293 CASRN: 149-57-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L12

M4ID: 30005734

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-30.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.114 MAX_MED: 0.164 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Ethylhexyl diphenyl phosphate

CHID: 25300 CASRN: 1241-94-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G17

M4ID: 30005849

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-12.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.15 MAX_MED: 0.275 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Formamide

CHID: 25337 CASRN: 75-12-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K20

M4ID: 30005750

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-28.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0767 MAX_MED: 0.139 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Hydroxy-2-methylpropanenitrile

CHID: 25427 CASRN: 75-86-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G20

M4ID: 30005462

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1.29	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0468 MAX_MED: -0.0143 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 6-Hydroxy-2-naphthyl disulfide

CHID: 25429 CASRN: 6088-51-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D13

M4ID: 30005541

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-25.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0564 MAX_MED: 0.036 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Hydroxyurea

CHID: 25438 CASRN: 127-07-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F24

M4ID: 30005482

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-12.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00573 MAX_MED: -0.0127 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 3-Methylbutyl acetate

CHID: 25453 CASRN: 123-92-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M17

M4ID: 30005705

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.222 MAX_MED: 0.157 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Isopentyl alcohol

CHID: 25469 CASRN: 123-51-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N19

M4ID: 30005679

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.13 MAX_MED: 0.121 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Isopropyl acetate

CHID: 25478 CASRN: 108-21-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P20

M4ID: 30005630

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	15.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.215 MAX_MED: -0.194 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Linalool

CHID: 25502 CASRN: 78-70-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G23

M4ID: 30005843

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-8.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.22 MAX_MED: 0.237 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Linoleic acid

CHID: 25505 CASRN: 60-33-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C08

M4ID: 30005954

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.114 MAX_MED: 0.149 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Maltol

CHID: 25523 CASRN: 118-71-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B21

M4ID: 30005965

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-36.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0792 MAX_MED: 0.0945 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Methyl 2-aminobenzoate
 CHID: 25567 CASRN: 134-20-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H04
 M4ID: 30005454

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0153 MAX_MED: -0.103 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: N,N'-Methylenebisacrylamide

CHID: 25595 CASRN: 110-26-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I15

M4ID: 30005419

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.473 MAX_MED: 0.361 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Ethoxyaniline

CHID: 25864 CASRN: 156-43-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A09

M4ID: 30005617

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.17 MAX_MED: 0.122 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Ethyl 3-phenylglycidate

CHID: 25886 CASRN: 121-39-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D01

M4ID: 30005937

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-44.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.11	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0829 MAX_MED: 0.0981 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: N-Phenyl-1,4-benzenediamine

CHID: 25895 CASRN: 101-54-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I08

M4ID: 30005810

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.325 MAX_MED: 0.269 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Tetrachlorophthalic anhydride

CHID: 26102 CASRN: 117-08-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I03

M4ID: 30005815

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.106 MAX_MED: 0.0955 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Tolyltriazole

CHID: 26171 CASRN: 29385-43-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N11

M4ID: 30005687

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-10.98	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.182 MAX_MED: 0.181 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Triethylene glycol dimethyl ether

CHID: 26224 CASRN: 112-49-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M01

M4ID: 30005337

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-11.17	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.146 MAX_MED: 0.157 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Triphenyl phosphite

CHID: 26252 CASRN: 101-02-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H17

M4ID: 30005441

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.17	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.203 MAX_MED: 0.199 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Camphene

CHID: 26488 CASRN: 79-92-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C23

M4ID: 30005939

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-17.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.216 MAX_MED: 0.224 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Phthalimide

CHID: 26514 CASRN: 85-41-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P08

M4ID: 30005258

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	6.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0153 MAX_MED: 0.0392 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Symclosene

CHID: 26523 CASRN: 87-90-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I04

M4ID: 30005430

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	14.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00923 MAX_MED: -0.113 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Triethylene glycol bis(2-ethylhexanoate)

CHID: 26564 CASRN: 94-28-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F03

M4ID: 30005503

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0732 MAX_MED: 0.0272 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-tert-Butylcyclohexanol

CHID: 26623 CASRN: 98-52-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B13

M4ID: 30005589

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-32.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.121 MAX_MED: 0.129 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,3-Diisopropylbenzene

CHID: 26640 CASRN: 99-62-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P19

M4ID: 30005631

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-3.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0501 MAX_MED: -0.0421 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,3-Benzenedicarbonyl dichloride

CHID: 26641 CASRN: 99-63-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P07

M4ID: 30005259

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-6.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0118 MAX_MED: 0.0217 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: p-Cymene

CHID: 26645 CASRN: 99-87-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L09

M4ID: 30005353

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	14.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.27 MAX_MED: 0.205 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 3-Pyridinecarbonitrile
 CHID: 26665 CASRN: 100-54-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B18
 M4ID: 30005584

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-1.77	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0397 MAX_MED: 0.00307 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-(Phenylmethylene)octanal

CHID: 26684 CASRN: 101-86-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J16

M4ID: 30005778

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	38.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.43	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.208 MAX_MED: -0.156 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Triacetin

CHID: 26691 CASRN: 102-76-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K22

M4ID: 30005748

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-21.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.161 MAX_MED: 0.2 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Ethylhexyl acetate

CHID: 26694 CASRN: 103-09-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D03

M4ID: 30005935

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-29.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0426 MAX_MED: 0.0875 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: (2Z)-3,7-Dimethylocta-2,6-dien-1-ol

CHID: 26728 CASRN: 106-25-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B18

M4ID: 30005968

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-25.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0223 MAX_MED: 0.0276 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 3-Methylaniline

CHID: 26792 CASRN: 108-44-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L18

M4ID: 30005728

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-10.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.204 MAX_MED: 0.274 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Benzenethiol

CHID: 26811 CASRN: 108-98-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M04

M4ID: 30005718

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0748 MAX_MED: -0.115 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Isopropyl tetradecanoate

CHID: 26838 CASRN: 110-27-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B06

M4ID: 30005980

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-33.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.07 MAX_MED: 0.0435 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Methyl decanoate

CHID: 26842 CASRN: 110-42-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P21

M4ID: 30005245

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	41.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.43	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.124 MAX_MED: 0.199 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Methyl octanoate

CHID: 26864 CASRN: 111-11-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J21

M4ID: 30005389

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	24.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.318 MAX_MED: 0.264 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Hexamethyleneimine

CHID: 26879 CASRN: 111-49-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M19

M4ID: 30005319

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	27.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.285 MAX_MED: 0.256 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,2-Ethanedio1 diacetate

CHID: 26880 CASRN: 111-55-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N18

M4ID: 30005296

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1.84	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.227 MAX_MED: 0.124 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-[2-(2-Methoxyethoxy)ethoxy]ethanol

CHID: 26912 CASRN: 112-35-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H17

M4ID: 30005825

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-24.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.172 MAX_MED: 0.175 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1-Undecanol

CHID: 26915 CASRN: 112-42-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G15

M4ID: 30005467

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.298 MAX_MED: 0.203 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Tetraethylene glycol
 CHID: 26922 CASRN: 112-60-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E17
 M4ID: 30005897

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-1.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0339 MAX_MED: -0.0386 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Pentaerythritol

CHID: 26943 CASRN: 115-77-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M13

M4ID: 30005709

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.22	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.00164 MAX_MED: -0.0613 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Methoxybenzaldehyde

CHID: 26997 CASRN: 123-11-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B23

M4ID: 30005963

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-20.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0131 MAX_MED: -0.0142 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Naphthalenol

CHID: 27061 CASRN: 135-19-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K10

M4ID: 30005760

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-25.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.193 MAX_MED: 0.213 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Sodium phenolate

CHID: 27072 CASRN: 139-02-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F07

M4ID: 30005499

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-10.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.27 MAX_MED: 0.33 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Bis(2-ethylhexyl) maleate

CHID: 27094 CASRN: 142-16-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L03

M4ID: 30005743

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-30.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0372 MAX_MED: 0.0346 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1H-1,2,4-Triazole

CHID: 27131 CASRN: 288-88-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078015

M4ID: 30005659

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	17.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0496 MAX_MED: -0.0102 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,3-Cyclopentadiene
 CHID: 27191 CASRN: 542-92-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J20
 M4ID: 30005390

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.157 MAX_MED: 0.0925 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: N-Methylphthalimide

CHID: 27198 CASRN: 550-44-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P08

M4ID: 30005642

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	22.15	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.228 MAX_MED: -0.205 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Methyl isothiocyanate

CHID: 27204 CASRN: 556-61-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G24

M4ID: 30005458

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-42.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.097 MAX_MED: 0.219 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Octamethylcyclotetrasiloxane

CHID: 27205 CASRN: 556-67-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G14

M4ID: 30005468

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00578 MAX_MED: -0.0623 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2,6-Diethylaniline

CHID: 27218 CASRN: 579-66-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091001

M4ID: 30005289

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-1.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.236 MAX_MED: 0.212 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Pyrrolidinone

CHID: 27246 CASRN: 616-45-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H19

M4ID: 30005439

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.162 MAX_MED: 0.191 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Isopropyl formate

CHID: 27258 CASRN: 625-55-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F03

M4ID: 30005887

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-24.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.00215 MAX_MED: -0.0135 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Pentyl acetate

CHID: 27263 CASRN: 628-63-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J23

M4ID: 30005771

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-24.41	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.152 MAX_MED: 0.156 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1-Phenoxy-2-propanol
 CHID: 27312 CASRN: 770-35-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H20
 M4ID: 30005438

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	4.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0617 MAX_MED: 0.0866 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Ammonium carbamate

CHID: 27360 CASRN: 1111-78-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N05

M4ID: 30005693

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-4.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0597 MAX_MED: -0.0743 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Diisooctyl adipate

CHID: 27388 CASRN: 1330-86-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A13

M4ID: 30005997

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.184 MAX_MED: 0.158 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Phenolsulfonic acid

CHID: 27390 CASRN: 1333-39-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B07

M4ID: 30005595

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-30.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.161 MAX_MED: 0.15 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: N,N-Dimethylacetoacetamide

CHID: 27454 CASRN: 2044-64-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L05

M4ID: 30005357

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.143 MAX_MED: 0.123 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Thiocarbazine

CHID: 27461 CASRN: 2231-57-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I20

M4ID: 30005414

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	4.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.111 MAX_MED: 0.103 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-(2H-Benzotriazol-2-yl)-4-methylphenol

CHID: 27479 CASRN: 2440-22-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F15

M4ID: 30005875

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0781 MAX_MED: 0.109 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2,3-Diaminotoluene

CHID: 27494 CASRN: 2687-25-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M10

M4ID: 30005712

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-3.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.104 MAX_MED: 0.0587 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2,4-D sodium salt

CHID: 27496 CASRN: 2702-72-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H18

M4ID: 30005824

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-7.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.114 MAX_MED: 0.07 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Potassium 2-ethylhexanoate

CHID: 27525 CASRN: 3164-85-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G19

M4ID: 30005463

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-8.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.127 MAX_MED: 0.108 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: N-Butylbenzenesulfonamide

CHID: 27540 CASRN: 3622-84-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H09

M4ID: 30005449

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-11.73	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.247 MAX_MED: 0.267 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Chlorobenzotrichloride

CHID: 27593 CASRN: 5216-25-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P01

M4ID: 30005265

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-18.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.000805 MAX_MED: 0.0303 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 3-Phenoxybenzenemethanol

CHID: 27756 CASRN: 13826-35-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L22

M4ID: 30005724

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-28.38	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.135 MAX_MED: 0.15 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propanesulfonic acid

CHID: 27770 CASRN: 15214-89-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L18

M4ID: 30005344

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-7.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.192 MAX_MED: 0.133 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dicyclohexyl sodium sulfosuccinate

CHID: 27826 CASRN: 23386-52-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M16

M4ID: 30005322

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	26.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.23 MAX_MED: 0.268 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Ammonium xylene sulfonate

CHID: 27899 CASRN: 26447-10-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C04

M4ID: 30005958

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0825 MAX_MED: -0.0766 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Neodecanoic acid

CHID: 27916 CASRN: 26896-20-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H07

M4ID: 30005451

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.342 MAX_MED: 0.264 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dodecylbenzene sulfonate triethanolamine(1:1)

CHID: 27932 CASRN: 27323-41-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C01

M4ID: 30005577

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-25.41	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.147 MAX_MED: 0.246 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether

CHID: 27983 CASRN: 34590-94-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F23

M4ID: 30005867

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-9.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00483 MAX_MED: 0.0903 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1-Hexadecanol

CHID: 27991 CASRN: 36653-82-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H08

M4ID: 30005450

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0999 MAX_MED: 0.0999 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dichlormid

CHID: 27997 CASRN: 37764-25-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D11

M4ID: 30005927

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-16.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0276 MAX_MED: -0.0147 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: DINP branched

CHID: 28665 CASRN: 68515-48-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H03

M4ID: 30005839

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-22.05	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0236 MAX_MED: 0.0733 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 3,7-Dimethyl-3-octanol

CHID: 29110 CASRN: 78-69-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F13

M4ID: 30005877

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.15 MAX_MED: -0.156 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Tetrahydrofurfuryl alcohol

CHID: 29128 CASRN: 97-99-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078004

M4ID: 30005670

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	18.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.16 MAX_MED: -0.158 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Cyclopentanone

CHID: 29154 CASRN: 120-92-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I04

M4ID: 30005814

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.042 MAX_MED: -0.0851 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-(Phenylmethylene)-heptanal

CHID: 29157 CASRN: 122-40-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J24

M4ID: 30005770

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-32.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0347 MAX_MED: 0.0739 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2,6,8-Trimethyl-4-nonanol

CHID: 29159 CASRN: 123-17-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J15

M4ID: 30005779

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0835 MAX_MED: 0.166 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 3-Bromo-1-chloro-5,5-dimethylhydantoin

CHID: 29162 CASRN: 126-06-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E07

M4ID: 30005523

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-7.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0877 MAX_MED: 0.0546 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Methylpent-3-en-2-one

CHID: 29170 CASRN: 141-79-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A03

M4ID: 30006007

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-27.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.282 MAX_MED: 0.276 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Methylionone

CHID: 29214 CASRN: 1335-46-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P17

M4ID: 30005633

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0978 MAX_MED: -0.0499 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Clopyralid

CHID: 29221 CASRN: 1702-17-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D04

M4ID: 30005550

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.112 MAX_MED: -0.127 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Triethoxyoctylsilane

CHID: 29246 CASRN: 2943-75-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091008

M4ID: 30005282

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0438 MAX_MED: -0.00715 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Glyceryl stearate

CHID: 29304 CASRN: 11099-07-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D02

M4ID: 30005936

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-29.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0099 MAX_MED: 0.0849 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Acetyl cedrene

CHID: 29353 CASRN: 32388-55-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B17

M4ID: 30005969

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0715 MAX_MED: 0.0275 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Diazolidinyl urea

CHID: 29559 CASRN: 78491-02-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J18

M4ID: 30005392

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-4.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.247 MAX_MED: 0.301 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Methacrylamide

CHID: 29600 CASRN: 79-39-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J19

M4ID: 30005775

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-7.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.253 MAX_MED: 0.24 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Thiocyanic acid, ammonium salt

CHID: 29653 CASRN: 1762-95-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M24

M4ID: 30005314

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	24.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.379 MAX_MED: 0.412 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 3,5,5-Trimethyl-1-hexanol

CHID: 29661 CASRN: 3452-97-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C23

M4ID: 30005555

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.201 MAX_MED: 0.214 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Silica

CHID: 29677 CASRN: 7631-86-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J17

M4ID: 30005777

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-41.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0875 MAX_MED: 0.0619 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,2-Propanediol monobutyl ether

CHID: 29755 CASRN: 29387-86-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I15

M4ID: 30005803

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.209 MAX_MED: 0.302 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Fenofibrate

CHID: 29874 CASRN: 49562-28-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H05

M4ID: 30005837

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-47.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0834 MAX_MED: 0.0662 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 8:2 Fluorotelomer alcohol

CHID: 29904 CASRN: 678-39-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E02

M4ID: 30005528

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.128 MAX_MED: -0.109 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dipentyl phthalate

CHID: 31131 CASRN: 131-18-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N20

M4ID: 30005294

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	37.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.43	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.36 MAX_MED: 0.151 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Perfluorooctanoic acid
 CHID: 31865 CASRN: 335-67-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G02
 M4ID: 30005480

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.17	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.121 MAX_MED: 0.0152 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Butralin

CHID: 32337 CASRN: 33629-47-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C17

M4ID: 30005561

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-1.98	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0352 MAX_MED: 0.132 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Clodinafop-propargyl

CHID: 32354 CASRN: 105512-06-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B04

M4ID: 30005598

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-1.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.015 MAX_MED: -0.0763 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Clomazone

CHID: 32355 CASRN: 81777-89-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P09

M4ID: 30005257

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	19.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0372 MAX_MED: -0.0774 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dichlobenil

CHID: 32365 CASRN: 1194-65-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L21

M4ID: 30005725

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	10.17	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.249 MAX_MED: 0.281 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dimethenamid

CHID: 32376 CASRN: 87674-68-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G23

M4ID: 30005459

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.42	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.314 MAX_MED: 0.286 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Ethalfluralin

CHID: 32386 CASRN: 55283-68-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M22

M4ID: 30005316

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	35.99	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.42	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.341 MAX_MED: 0.148 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Formetanate hydrochloride

CHID: 32405 CASRN: 23422-53-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I16

M4ID: 30005418

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.225 MAX_MED: 0.234 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Profenofos

CHID: 32464 CASRN: 41198-08-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K05

M4ID: 30005381

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-1.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.316 MAX_MED: 0.334 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Triclopyr

CHID: 32497 CASRN: 55335-06-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E06

M4ID: 30005908

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	14.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.138 MAX_MED: -0.124 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Triclosan

CHID: 32498 CASRN: 3380-34-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091006

M4ID: 30005284

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.32 MAX_MED: 0.241 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Hydroxyethyl octyl sulfide

CHID: 32516 CASRN: 3547-33-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F16

M4ID: 30005490

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0955 MAX_MED: -0.113 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Acibenzolar-S-methyl

CHID: 32519 CASRN: 135158-54-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A11

M4ID: 30005999

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-1.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.389 MAX_MED: 0.389 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,2-Benzisothiazolin-3-one

CHID: 32523 CASRN: 2634-33-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E22

M4ID: 30005892

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-18.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0474 MAX_MED: -0.0394 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Etridiazole

CHID: 32547 CASRN: 2593-15-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E08

M4ID: 30005522

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	17.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.141 MAX_MED: -0.107 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Fenhexamid

CHID: 32549 CASRN: 126833-17-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E20

M4ID: 30005894

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.358 MAX_MED: 0.383 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Tefluthrin

CHID: 32577 CASRN: 79538-32-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078013

M4ID: 30005661

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	16.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.204 MAX_MED: 0.252 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Cyproconazole

CHID: 32601 CASRN: 94361-06-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J03

M4ID: 30005791

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-3.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.131 MAX_MED: 0.162 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Fenitrothion

CHID: 32613 CASRN: 122-14-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091018

M4ID: 30005272

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.312 MAX_MED: 0.336 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Pymetrozine

CHID: 32637 CASRN: 123312-89-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I20

M4ID: 30005798

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-50.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.109 MAX_MED: 0.136 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Pyridate

CHID: 32639 CASRN: 55512-33-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E13

M4ID: 30005517

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-6.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.241 MAX_MED: 0.291 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Pyriproxyfen

CHID: 32640 CASRN: 95737-68-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G21

M4ID: 30005461

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	13.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.219 MAX_MED: 0.208 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: N-Ethylperfluorooctanesulfonamide

CHID: 32646 CASRN: 4151-50-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D04

M4ID: 30005934

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-8.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0061 MAX_MED: -0.0743 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-(Thiocyanomethylthio)benzothiazole

CHID: 32647 CASRN: 21564-17-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K10

M4ID: 30005376

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-3.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.19 MAX_MED: 0.133 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Tetramethrin

CHID: 32649 CASRN: 7696-12-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091004

M4ID: 30005286

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	22.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.027 MAX_MED: -0.0743 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Indoxacarb

CHID: 32690 CASRN: 173584-44-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H09

M4ID: 30005833

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-20.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.135 MAX_MED: 0.135 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Amino-1,2,4-triazole
 CHID: 33058 CASRN: 584-13-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P24
 M4ID: 30005242

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	29.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.184 MAX_MED: 0.0462 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Cyclopentanol

CHID: 33371 CASRN: 96-41-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A05

M4ID: 30006005

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-38.97	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.286 MAX_MED: 0.268 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Nilutamide

CHID: 34165 CASRN: 63612-50-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L06

M4ID: 30005740

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.66	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.372 MAX_MED: 0.309 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Tepraloxydim

CHID: 34252 CASRN: 149979-41-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C09

M4ID: 30005569

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-16.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.173 MAX_MED: 0.185 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Chlorophenoxyacetic acid

CHID: 34282 CASRN: 122-88-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N08

M4ID: 30005306

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12.21	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.185 MAX_MED: 0.154 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Fluroxypyr-meptyl

CHID: 34303 CASRN: 81406-37-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A21

M4ID: 30005605

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	14.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.132 MAX_MED: -0.155 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Denatonium saccharide

CHID: 34361 CASRN: 90823-38-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D19

M4ID: 30005535

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-25.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0419 MAX_MED: 0.00137 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Boscalid

CHID: 34392 CASRN: 188425-85-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B21

M4ID: 30005581

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0654 MAX_MED: -0.0326 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Buprofezin

CHID: 34401 CASRN: 69327-76-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091003

M4ID: 30005287

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	18.06	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.127 MAX_MED: 0.155 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Butachlor

CHID: 34402 CASRN: 23184-66-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P11

M4ID: 30005255

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-10.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.046 MAX_MED: 0.0789 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Cinmethylin

CHID: 34456 CASRN: 87818-31-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F20

M4ID: 30005870

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-8.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.06 MAX_MED: -0.0497 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Cyhalofop-butyl

CHID: 34503 CASRN: 122008-85-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E21

M4ID: 30005893

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0784 MAX_MED: 0.0654 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Desmedipham

CHID: 34518 CASRN: 13684-56-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M14

M4ID: 30005708

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	24.88	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.33	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.139 MAX_MED: -0.0793 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dinotefuran

CHID: 34549 CASRN: 165252-70-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K08

M4ID: 30005378

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.139 MAX_MED: 0.0577 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Bromo-4-hydroxyacetophenone

CHID: 34576 CASRN: 2491-38-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D07

M4ID: 30005547

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.5	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.15 MAX_MED: 0.216 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Fluazifop-butyl

CHID: 34612 CASRN: 69806-50-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I17

M4ID: 30005417

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-25.22	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.234 MAX_MED: 0.221 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Flufenpyr-ethyl

CHID: 34618 CASRN: 188489-07-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I07

M4ID: 30005811

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-20.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.18 MAX_MED: 0.217 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Imazamox

CHID: 34664 CASRN: 114311-32-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J07

M4ID: 30005403

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	4.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.259 MAX_MED: 0.259 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Isazofos

CHID: 34676 CASRN: 42509-80-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I18

M4ID: 30005416

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-28.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.177 MAX_MED: 0.184 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Isoxaflutole

CHID: 34723 CASRN: 141112-29-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091024

M4ID: 30005266

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	26.13	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.201 MAX_MED: 0.155 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Milbemectin (mixture of 70% Milbemcin A4, 30% I

CHID: 34742 CASRN: NOCAS_34742

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D01

M4ID: 30005553

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-12.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.204 MAX_MED: 0.202 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Penoxsulam

CHID: 34803 CASRN: 219714-96-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C18

M4ID: 30005944

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-17.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.00241 MAX_MED: -0.0051 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Monocrotophos

CHID: 34816 CASRN: 6923-22-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091009

M4ID: 30005281

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	21.98	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.153 MAX_MED: 0.204 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Azamethiphos

CHID: 34818 CASRN: 35575-96-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K03

M4ID: 30005383

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	25.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.366 MAX_MED: 0.373 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Propamocarb hydrochloride

CHID: 34849 CASRN: 25606-41-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F17

M4ID: 30005489

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-27.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.103 MAX_MED: 0.0674 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Fluazifop-P-butyl

CHID: 34855 CASRN: 79241-46-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F09

M4ID: 30005497

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-12.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.146 MAX_MED: 0.128 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Chloridazon

CHID: 34872 CASRN: 1698-60-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E04

M4ID: 30005526

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	14.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.185 MAX_MED: -0.115 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Pyrimethanil

CHID: 34877 CASRN: 53112-28-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P04

M4ID: 30005262

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	21.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.128 MAX_MED: -0.203 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Spiromesifen

CHID: 34929 CASRN: 283594-90-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G01

M4ID: 30005865

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.242 MAX_MED: 0.268 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Thiamethoxam

CHID: 34962 CASRN: 153719-23-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A17

M4ID: 30005609

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-20.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.00599 MAX_MED: 0.0633 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Thymo1

CHID: 34972 CASRN: 89-83-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E13

M4ID: 30005901

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0705 MAX_MED: 0.245 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Tralkoxydim

CHID: 34973 CASRN: 87820-88-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L10

M4ID: 30005352

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.186 MAX_MED: 0.126 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Sodium warfarin

CHID: 35010 CASRN: 129-06-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L17

M4ID: 30005729

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	6.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.328 MAX_MED: 0.278 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1-(Hydroxymethyl)-5,5-dimethylhydantoin

CHID: 35152 CASRN: 116-25-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D17

M4ID: 30005537

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-12.75	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0123 MAX_MED: -0.024 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: alpha-Ionone

CHID: 35160 CASRN: 127-41-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D14

M4ID: 30005924

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	10.75	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0563 MAX_MED: 0.00522 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Allethrin

CHID: 35180 CASRN: 584-79-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P05

M4ID: 30005261

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.119 MAX_MED: -0.0819 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,4-Dimethylnaphthalene

CHID: 35423 CASRN: 571-58-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K21

M4ID: 30005749

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.319 MAX_MED: 0.304 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-(8-Heptadecenyl)-2-imidazoline-1-ethanol

CHID: 36112 CASRN: 95-38-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K24

M4ID: 30005362

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.295 MAX_MED: 0.292 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Hexadecyltrimethylammonium bromide

CHID: 37028 CASRN: 57-09-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J13

M4ID: 30005781

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.49	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.239 MAX_MED: 0.357 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Perfluoroheptanoic acid

CHID: 37303 CASRN: 375-85-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N16

M4ID: 30005298

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	31.09	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.131 MAX_MED: 0.114 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Deisopropylatrazine

CHID: 37495 CASRN: 1007-28-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E03

M4ID: 30005527

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0897 MAX_MED: 0.0674 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Fenuron

CHID: 37551 CASRN: 101-42-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K08

M4ID: 30005762

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.118 MAX_MED: 0.186 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Potassium perfluorohexanesulfonate

CHID: 37709 CASRN: 3871-99-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091002

M4ID: 30005288

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-8.78	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0597 MAX_MED: 0.0722 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 3-Phenoxybenzoic acid

CHID: 38321 CASRN: 3739-38-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M15

M4ID: 30005323

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	23.32	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.33	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.238 MAX_MED: 0.111 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Chlorpyrifos oxon

CHID: 38666 CASRN: 5598-15-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B10

M4ID: 30005592

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.138 MAX_MED: 0.0859 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,4-Cyclohexanedicarboxylic acid

CHID: 38788 CASRN: 1076-97-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H12

M4ID: 30005446

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0341 MAX_MED: 0.0341 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Fluorescein

CHID: 38887 CASRN: 2321-07-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D24

M4ID: 30005914

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0553 MAX_MED: 0.0583 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Ethyl propionate

CHID: 40110 CASRN: 105-37-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B03

M4ID: 30005983

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-33.91	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0853 MAX_MED: 0.0681 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Ethyl heptanoate

CHID: 40112 CASRN: 106-30-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I16

M4ID: 30005802

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	36.23	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.41	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.235 MAX_MED: -0.23 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Trifloxysulfuron-sodium

CHID: 40222 CASRN: 199119-58-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P23

M4ID: 30005243

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	23.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.33	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.206 MAX_MED: 0.254 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Butylene carbonate

CHID: 40342 CASRN: 4437-85-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L19

M4ID: 30005343

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	14.01	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.185 MAX_MED: 0.153 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Isoxadifen-ethyl

CHID: 40360 CASRN: 163520-33-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H13

M4ID: 30005445

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-9.76	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.119 MAX_MED: 0.0683 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Niclosamide

CHID: 40362 CASRN: 50-65-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A24

M4ID: 30005602

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	16.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.365 MAX_MED: 0.416 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Butyl benzoate

CHID: 40694 CASRN: 136-60-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B15

M4ID: 30005587

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-20.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0309 MAX_MED: 0.079 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Trimethoxyphenylsilane

CHID: 40700 CASRN: 2996-92-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D16

M4ID: 30005538

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0914 MAX_MED: -0.0925 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Cyclohexylcyclohexanone

CHID: 40721 CASRN: 92-68-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F12

M4ID: 30005878

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0121 MAX_MED: -0.0256 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-tert-Butyl-4-methoxyphenol

CHID: 40788 CASRN: 121-00-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B02

M4ID: 30005600

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.127 MAX_MED: 0.15 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Pyridoxine hydrochloride

CHID: 40792 CASRN: 58-56-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078009

M4ID: 30005665

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.192 MAX_MED: 0.187 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Sodium iodide

CHID: 41125 CASRN: 7681-82-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L12

M4ID: 30005350

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-8.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0406 MAX_MED: 0.155 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,3,5-Triisopropylbenzene

CHID: 41232 CASRN: 717-74-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G12

M4ID: 30005470

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-20.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00615 MAX_MED: -0.00615 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,3-Diphenyl-1,3-propanedione

CHID: 41247 CASRN: 120-46-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A17

M4ID: 30005993

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-22.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.375 MAX_MED: 0.371 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Hexyl-1-decanol

CHID: 41265 CASRN: 2425-77-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091012

M4ID: 30005278

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	15.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0176 MAX_MED: -0.0396 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1-Phenyl-1H-pyrrole-2,5-dione

CHID: 41274 CASRN: 941-69-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C01

M4ID: 30005961

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-28.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.28 MAX_MED: 0.292 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2'-Acetonaphthone

CHID: 41389 CASRN: 93-08-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G22

M4ID: 30005844

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0454 MAX_MED: 0.0364 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Methylbutyl isovalerate

CHID: 41440 CASRN: 2445-77-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F11

M4ID: 30005879

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-51.56	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.1	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0841 MAX_MED: 0.0685 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: (3Z)-3-Hexenyl acetate

CHID: 41484 CASRN: 3681-71-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E23

M4ID: 30005891

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-8.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.264 MAX_MED: 0.262 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 3-Phenylhexane

CHID: 41492 CASRN: 4468-42-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I09

M4ID: 30005809

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-27.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.149 MAX_MED: 0.167 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Morpholinepropanamine

CHID: 41521 CASRN: 123-00-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B10

M4ID: 30005976

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1.09	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0303 MAX_MED: -0.0778 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 7-Ethyl-2-methyl-4-undecanol sulfate, sodium salt

CHID: 41530 CASRN: 139-88-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N19

M4ID: 30005295

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	33.44	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.166 MAX_MED: 0.0672 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dihydromyrcenol

CHID: 41557 CASRN: 53219-21-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L16

M4ID: 30005730

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	16.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0466 MAX_MED: -0.111 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Pentyl butyrate

CHID: 41604 CASRN: 540-18-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A04

M4ID: 30006006

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.22	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0776 MAX_MED: -0.0605 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Arabinose

CHID: 41610 CASRN: 147-81-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C07

M4ID: 30005571

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.15	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.322 MAX_MED: 0.381 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Benodanil

CHID: 41623 CASRN: 15310-01-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D15

M4ID: 30005539

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0694 MAX_MED: 0.103 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Sodium m-xylene-4-sulfonate

CHID: 41639 CASRN: 827-21-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G20

M4ID: 30005846

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.54	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00278 MAX_MED: -0.00869 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: C.I. Acid Yellow 34, monosodium salt

CHID: 41646 CASRN: 6359-90-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E14

M4ID: 30005900

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	16.04	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.131 MAX_MED: 0.209 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Hydroxybenzonitrile
 CHID: 41661 CASRN: 611-20-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G07
 M4ID: 30005475

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.26	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.329 MAX_MED: 0.301 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Benzyl cinnamate

CHID: 41663 CASRN: 103-41-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B20

M4ID: 30005966

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-26.1	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0121 MAX_MED: -0.032 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Butylphthalenesulfonic acid sodium salt

CHID: 41703 CASRN: 25638-17-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F05

M4ID: 30005885

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-35.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0266 MAX_MED: 0.108 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: C.I. Acid Yellow 3 disodium salt

CHID: 41721 CASRN: 8004-92-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F14

M4ID: 30005492

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.75	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.321 MAX_MED: 0.341 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Citronella l

CHID: 41790 CASRN: 106-23-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C03

M4ID: 30005959

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-22.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.349 MAX_MED: 0.338 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dibutyl decanedioate

CHID: 41847 CASRN: 109-43-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E03

M4ID: 30005911

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.85	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.222 MAX_MED: 0.294 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Diethyl phosphite

CHID: 41861 CASRN: 762-04-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N15

M4ID: 30005683

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.152 MAX_MED: -0.102 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dimethylbenzylcarbinyll acetate

CHID: 41877 CASRN: 151-05-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L15

M4ID: 30005731

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	4.57	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0398 MAX_MED: 0.024 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Diphenyl phosphite

CHID: 41889 CASRN: 4712-55-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E20

M4ID: 30005510

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	23.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.33	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.151 MAX_MED: -0.173 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Ethyl diethanolamine
 CHID: 41955 CASRN: 139-87-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E19
 M4ID: 30005511

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-4.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0325 MAX_MED: 0.0417 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Ethyl orthoformate

CHID: 41957 CASRN: 122-51-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P05

M4ID: 30005645

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	6.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.167 MAX_MED: -0.185 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Flufenoxuron

CHID: 41978 CASRN: 101463-69-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E01

M4ID: 30005913

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-16.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.152 MAX_MED: 0.116 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Fluoroacetic acid

CHID: 41981 CASRN: 144-49-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B20

M4ID: 30005582

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0989 MAX_MED: 0.0328 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Isoborneol

CHID: 42060 CASRN: 124-76-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091021

M4ID: 30005269

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	42.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.46	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.245 MAX_MED: 0.209 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Isobornyl propanoate

CHID: 42062 CASRN: 2756-56-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L11

M4ID: 30005351

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.394 MAX_MED: 0.394 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Diphenylmercury(II)

CHID: 42130 CASRN: 587-85-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E12

M4ID: 30005902

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0244 MAX_MED: 0.0161 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Dodecylmorpholine

CHID: 42171 CASRN: 1541-81-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A23

M4ID: 30005603

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-7.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.11 MAX_MED: 0.133 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: N,N-Diisopropylaniline

CHID: 42189 CASRN: 4107-98-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N08

M4ID: 30005690

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.127 MAX_MED: -0.106 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: N,N'-Dimethylthiourea
 CHID: 42191 CASRN: 534-13-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091016
 M4ID: 30005274

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	23.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.106 MAX_MED: 0.212 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: N-Methyldioctylamine

CHID: 42209 CASRN: 4455-26-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091010

M4ID: 30005280

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	23.59	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.125 MAX_MED: -0.215 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Propylbenzene

CHID: 42219 CASRN: 103-65-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B11

M4ID: 30005975

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.15	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0612 MAX_MED: -0.0292 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dimethoxydimethylsilane
 CHID: 42379 CASRN: 1112-39-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I12
 M4ID: 30005422

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-33.79	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.113 MAX_MED: 0.113 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Sodium (2-pyridylthio)-N-oxide

CHID: 42390 CASRN: 3811-73-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E11

M4ID: 30005903

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-17.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.322 MAX_MED: 0.272 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Sulfosuccinic acid

CHID: 42426 CASRN: 5138-18-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P19

M4ID: 30005247

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	37.11	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0255 MAX_MED: -0.106 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Tetradecanoic acid, 2,3-dihydroxypropyl ester

CHID: 42454 CASRN: 589-68-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E14

M4ID: 30005516

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.061 MAX_MED: -0.0477 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Clove leaf oil

CHID: 44175 CASRN: 8000-34-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C09

M4ID: 30005953

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-21.62	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.275 MAX_MED: 0.41 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,2-Diphenylethanone

CHID: 44430 CASRN: 451-40-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L20

M4ID: 30005726

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-7.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.273 MAX_MED: 0.258 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: N,N-Dibutyl-N-methylbutan-1-aminium chloride

CHID: 44443 CASRN: 56375-79-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P09

M4ID: 30005641

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	22.43	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.18 MAX_MED: -0.166 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: C.I. Disperse Orange 37

CHID: 44538 CASRN: 13301-61-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D23

M4ID: 30005531

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	14.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.506 MAX_MED: 0.403 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2,6,10-Trimethyl-2,6,10-triazaundecane

CHID: 44564 CASRN: 3855-32-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L15

M4ID: 30005347

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	15.67	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.348 MAX_MED: 0.394 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 6:2 Fluorotelomer alcohol

CHID: 44572 CASRN: 647-42-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D02

M4ID: 30005552

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-4.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0198 MAX_MED: 0.00289 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: MON-4660

CHID: 44575 CASRN: 71526-07-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L13

M4ID: 30005733

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	6.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0195 MAX_MED: -0.0496 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-tert-Butyl-4-ethylphenol

CHID: 44581 CASRN: 96-70-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N04

M4ID: 30005310

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	30.89	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.331 MAX_MED: 0.195 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Glycidyl trimethylammonium chloride

CHID: 44643 CASRN: 3033-77-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F21

M4ID: 30005485

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-1.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0942 MAX_MED: 0.0932 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dibutyl nonanedioate

CHID: 44815 CASRN: 2917-73-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A02

M4ID: 30005624

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	6.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0338 MAX_MED: -0.0408 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Terpinyl propionate

CHID: 44833 CASRN: 80-27-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P15

M4ID: 30005635

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	26.51	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.33	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.253 MAX_MED: -0.186 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Triallyl trimellitate

CHID: 44901 CASRN: 2694-54-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H11

M4ID: 30005447

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-32.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.13	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.135 MAX_MED: 0.174 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Isopropyl triethanolamine titanate

CHID: 44928 CASRN: 36673-16-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C10

M4ID: 30005568

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0683 MAX_MED: -0.0824 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Octadecyl sulfate sodium salt

CHID: 47103 CASRN: 1120-04-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091013

M4ID: 30005277

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	28.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.392 MAX_MED: 0.264 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: tert-Butylbenzene

CHID: 47138 CASRN: 98-06-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F02

M4ID: 30005888

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.000867 MAX_MED: 0.0588 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: CI-1018

CHID: 47248 CASRN: NOCAS_47248

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F13

M4ID: 30005493

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-9.35	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0302 MAX_MED: 0.0412 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Zamifenacin

CHID: 47257 CASRN: 127308-82-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B24

M4ID: 30005962

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.05 MAX_MED: -0.0638 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Besonprodil

CHID: 47270 CASRN: 253450-09-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E02

M4ID: 30005912

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0264 MAX_MED: 0.00797 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: CP-409092

CHID: 47276 CASRN: 194098-25-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J01

M4ID: 30005793

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-38.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.12	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.184 MAX_MED: 0.167 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: CP-457677

CHID: 47278 CASRN: 214535-77-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N01

M4ID: 30005697

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-7.61	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0496 MAX_MED: 0.0472 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: CP-607366

CHID: 47280 CASRN: 289716-94-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L01

M4ID: 30005745

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-24.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.214 MAX_MED: 0.192 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: CP-671305

CHID: 47282 CASRN: 445295-04-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K07

M4ID: 30005763

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-18.19	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.452 MAX_MED: 0.401 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: PHA-00543613

CHID: 47284 CASRN: 478149-53-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H01

M4ID: 30005457

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-2.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.222 MAX_MED: 0.225 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: UK-416244

CHID: 47290 CASRN: 402910-27-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M13

M4ID: 30005325

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	23.68	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.33	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.196 MAX_MED: 0.0477 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: CI-1044

CHID: 47291 CASRN: NOCAS_47291

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G08

M4ID: 30005858

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-12.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00645 MAX_MED: -0.00784 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Zenarestat

CHID: 47296 CASRN: 112733-06-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L24

M4ID: 30005722

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-9.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.196 MAX_MED: 0.198 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: CP-422935

CHID: 47299 CASRN: NOCAS_47299

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J01

M4ID: 30005409

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-11.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.181 MAX_MED: 0.211 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: CP-608039

CHID: 47305 CASRN: NOCAS_47305

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M02

M4ID: 30005720

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-7.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.108 MAX_MED: -0.0879 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: UK-156819

CHID: 47309 CASRN: 162706-14-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N09

M4ID: 30005305

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	18.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.16 MAX_MED: 0.158 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: GW473178E methyl benzene sulphonic acid

CHID: 47313 CASRN: 263553-33-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C13

M4ID: 30005565

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.186 MAX_MED: 0.239 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: HMR1426

CHID: 47338 CASRN: 262376-75-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B04

M4ID: 30005982

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-20.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0894 MAX_MED: 0.097 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: SR125047

CHID: 47342 CASRN: NOCAS_47342

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F01

M4ID: 30005889

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-17.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0637 MAX_MED: 0.108 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: SSR162369

CHID: 47346 CASRN: NOCAS_47346

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C05

M4ID: 30005957

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-32.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.322 MAX_MED: 0.36 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Volinanserin

CHID: 47363 CASRN: 139290-65-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P13

M4ID: 30005253

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	17.15	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0711 MAX_MED: -0.128 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: SSR 103800

CHID: 47364 CASRN: 1075752-90-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P01

M4ID: 30005649

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-12.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0796 MAX_MED: 0.0839 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: AVE3295

CHID: 47372 CASRN: 478263-98-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K02

M4ID: 30005768

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-13.69	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0794 MAX_MED: 0.0673 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: SAR377142

CHID: 47385 CASRN: NOCAS_47385

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N17

M4ID: 30005297

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	6.74	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.265 MAX_MED: 0.383 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Grinstad Soft-N-Safe

CHID: 47394 CASRN: NOCAS_47394

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078008

M4ID: 30005666

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0507 MAX_MED: -0.033 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Diisononyl cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate

CHID: 47395 CASRN: 166412-78-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B03

M4ID: 30005599

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-14.75	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0465 MAX_MED: 0.0452 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dexamethasone sodium phosphate

CHID: 47429 CASRN: 2392-39-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H05

M4ID: 30005453

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-21.08	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.222 MAX_MED: 0.233 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Potassium chlorate

CHID: 47448 CASRN: 3811-04-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H16

M4ID: 30005442

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.9	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0254 MAX_MED: 0.0995 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Hexanedioic acid, di-C7-9-branched and linear ;

CHID: 47517 CASRN: 68515-75-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K09

M4ID: 30005377

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	16.45	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.32 MAX_MED: 0.397 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: C10-21 alkanesulfonic acids phenyl esters

CHID: 47526 CASRN: 91082-17-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B09

M4ID: 30005977

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-7.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0243 MAX_MED: 0.0594 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Adipic acid, polypropyleneglycol, laurate

CHID: 47527 CASRN: 66456-53-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L08

M4ID: 30005738

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-12.33	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.17	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.134 MAX_MED: 0.134 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Benzyl octyl adipate

CHID: 47528 CASRN: 58394-64-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B14

M4ID: 30005588

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-27.58	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.14	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0261 MAX_MED: 0.0462 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Trioctyl trimellitate
 CHID: 47533 CASRN: 89-04-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L03
 M4ID: 30005359

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	22.77	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.33	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.109 MAX_MED: -0.049 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 3-Hydroxyfluorene

CHID: 47540 CASRN: 6344-67-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C20

M4ID: 30005942

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-16.55	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.422 MAX_MED: 0.341 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,4-Heptanolid

CHID: 47611 CASRN: 105-21-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J13

M4ID: 30005397

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.81	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.165 MAX_MED: 0.117 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Cremophor EL

CHID: 47696 CASRN: 61791-12-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L02

M4ID: 30005744

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-6.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0487 MAX_MED: -0.0427 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Igepal CO-890

CHID: 47708 CASRN: NOCAS_47708

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J08

M4ID: 30005786

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-7.36	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0661 MAX_MED: 0.109 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Octylparaben

CHID: 47957 CASRN: 1219-38-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B02

M4ID: 30005984

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	3.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.036 MAX_MED: 0.0379 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Melengestrol acetate

CHID: 48184 CASRN: 2919-66-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C15

M4ID: 30005947

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-0.16	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.263 MAX_MED: 0.348 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Lauryl gallate

CHID: 48189 CASRN: 1166-52-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H01

M4ID: 30005841

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-20.52	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.18	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.387 MAX_MED: 0.357 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Methyl abietate

CHID: 48190 CASRN: 127-25-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I14

M4ID: 30005420

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-9.14	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.19	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0299 MAX_MED: 0.0229 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Propylcyclohexanone

CHID: 48198 CASRN: 40649-36-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C14

M4ID: 30005948

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0538 MAX_MED: 0.0867 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Isopropyl phenyl ketone

CHID: 48202 CASRN: 611-70-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G15

M4ID: 30005851

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-7.46	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.3 MAX_MED: 0.317 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Chloropentylbenzene

CHID: 48206 CASRN: 79098-20-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C14

M4ID: 30005564

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1.89	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.22	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.112 MAX_MED: -0.0399 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Methyl 2-methylbenzoate

CHID: 48208 CASRN: 89-71-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N04

M4ID: 30005694

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.125 MAX_MED: -0.0831 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: PharmaGSID_48507

CHID: 48507 CASRN: NOCAS_48507

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I13

M4ID: 30005421

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	3.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.24	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.213 MAX_MED: 0.0637 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: PharmaGSID_48509

CHID: 48509 CASRN: NOCAS_48509

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B15

M4ID: 30005971

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.18	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.16	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.134 MAX_MED: 0.0601 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: HMR1171 trifluoroacetate (1:1)

CHID: 48522 CASRN: NOCAS_48522

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M08

M4ID: 30005714

HILL MODEL: Not applicable.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Not applicable.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-7.87	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0732 MAX_MED: -0.0414 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 4 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Carbofuran

CHID: 20249 CASRN: 1563-66-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P06

M4ID: 30005644

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	13.39	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.115 MAX_MED: -0.133 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Propham

CHID: 20766 CASRN: 122-42-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A10

M4ID: 30006000

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	30.8	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.00866 MAX_MED: -0.0247 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Methyl carbamate

CHID: 20834 CASRN: 598-55-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A22

M4ID: 30005604

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	25.89	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.33	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.109 MAX_MED: -0.0441 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Diethyl propanedioate

CHID: 21863 CASRN: 105-53-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F20

M4ID: 30005486

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	16.34	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0573 MAX_MED: 0.0102 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: EPN

CHID: 22174 CASRN: 2104-64-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078010

M4ID: 30005664

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	35.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.241 MAX_MED: -0.218 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Vinclozolin

CHID: 22361 CASRN: 50471-44-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F22

M4ID: 30005484

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.2e-12	-1.54	1.15
sd:	9.86e-07	93400	368000

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.53e-11	-1.7	1.51	-1.1	5.28
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	20.36	26.36	30.36
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	0.31	0.31	0.31

MAX_MEAN: 0.156 MAX_MED: 0.331 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 5alpha-Dihydrotestosterone

CHID: 22364 CASRN: 521-18-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C11

M4ID: 30005567

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.14e-11	0.418	1.4
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.44e-11	0.512	1.15	1.54	5.35
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	18.55	24.55	28.55
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	0.3	0.3	0.3

MAX_MEAN: 0.162 MAX_MED: 0.186 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Digoxin

CHID: 22934 CASRN: 20830-75-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F14

M4ID: 30005876

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	34.77	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.211 MAX_MED: -0.156 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Retinol

CHID: 23556 CASRN: 68-26-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H14

M4ID: 30005828

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.2	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.029 MAX_MED: 0.00967 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Polydimethylsiloxane

CHID: 23833 CASRN: 9016-00-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A12

M4ID: 30005614

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	35.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN:	-0.215	MAX_MED:	-0.166	BMAD:	0.14
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COFF:	0.421	HIT-CALL:	0	FITC:	7	ACTP:	0
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FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dicamba

CHID: 24018 CASRN: 1918-00-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A10

M4ID: 30005616

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	20.17	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0612 MAX_MED: -0.0433 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Diphenamid

CHID: 24072 CASRN: 957-51-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B12

M4ID: 30005590

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	19.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0756 MAX_MED: -0.0199 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Methamidophos

CHID: 24177 CASRN: 10265-92-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A04

M4ID: 30005622

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.94	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.26	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.056 MAX_MED: -0.0673 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Pendimethalin

CHID: 24245 CASRN: 40487-42-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P20

M4ID: 30005246

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	48.89	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.49	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.136 MAX_MED: -0.133 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dimethyl succinate

CHID: 25152 CASRN: 106-65-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A24

M4ID: 30005986

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12.71	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.137 MAX_MED: -0.119 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Myrcene

CHID: 25692 CASRN: 123-35-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E16

M4ID: 30005514

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	19.24	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.141 MAX_MED: -0.104 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Terephthalic acid

CHID: 26080 CASRN: 100-21-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B14

M4ID: 30005972

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	10.7	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0636 MAX_MED: 0.0838 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Theobromine

CHID: 26132 CASRN: 83-67-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P14

M4ID: 30005636

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	35.77	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.299 MAX_MED: -0.266 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Trimellitic anhydride

CHID: 26235 CASRN: 552-30-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G16

M4ID: 30005850

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	37.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.241 MAX_MED: -0.244 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Acetyl tributyl citrate

CHID: 26446 CASRN: 77-90-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H16

M4ID: 30005826

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	35.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.188 MAX_MED: -0.165 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,2,3,6-Tetrahydrophthalimide

CHID: 26513 CASRN: 85-40-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M16

M4ID: 30005706

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	27.98	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.35	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.187 MAX_MED: -0.0407 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Hydroxybenzoic acid

CHID: 26647 CASRN: 99-96-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L14

M4ID: 30005732

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	17.86	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.29	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.104 MAX_MED: -0.041 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Sodium dimethyldithiocarbamate

CHID: 27050 CASRN: 128-04-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P10

M4ID: 30005640

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	35.93	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.39	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.163 MAX_MED: -0.198 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Phenyl phosphorus dichloride

CHID: 27282 CASRN: 644-97-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D20

M4ID: 30005534

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-1.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.21	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0708 MAX_MED: -0.0571 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 3-(Methylthio)propanal

CHID: 27528 CASRN: 3268-49-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A20

M4ID: 30005606

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	24.25	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.32	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.152 MAX_MED: -0.148 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Sodium chloroacetate

CHID: 27550 CASRN: 3926-62-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091020

M4ID: 30005270

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	49.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.48	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.136 MAX_MED: -0.0431 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Malic acid

CHID: 27640 CASRN: 6915-15-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P12

M4ID: 30005638

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	27.83	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.34	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.224 MAX_MED: -0.158 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Glyceryl monooleate

CHID: 27875 CASRN: 25496-72-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P22

M4ID: 30005244

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.46e-11	-1.71	1.24
sd:	9.23e-06	30000	213000

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.75e-09	-1.65	2.58	-1.35	4.31
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	44.47	50.47	54.47
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	0.45	0.45	0.45

MAX_MEAN: 0.112 MAX_MED: 0.0139 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Diisodecyl hexanedioate

CHID: 27924 CASRN: 27178-16-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B24

M4ID: 30005578

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	3.12	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.23	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.124 MAX_MED: -0.152 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,1-Bis(3,4-dimethylphenyl)ethane

CHID: 29223 CASRN: 1742-14-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B16

M4ID: 30005970

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	24.3	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.33	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.138 MAX_MED: -0.178 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Tripropylene glycol monomethyl ether

CHID: 29329 CASRN: 25498-49-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K04

M4ID: 30005382

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	25.92	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.33	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: 0.0559 MAX_MED: -0.0249 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Glycoluril

CHID: 31380 CASRN: 496-46-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G02

M4ID: 30005864

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-8.28	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.2	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0223 MAX_MED: -0.00296 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4,5-Dichloro-3H-1,2-dithiol-3-one

CHID: 32518 CASRN: 1192-52-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F24

M4ID: 30005866

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.24e-13	-1.94	1.15
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.2e-12	-1.78	1.21	-0.885	5.01
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.65	14.65	18.65
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	0.26	0.26	0.26

MAX_MEAN: -0.0427 MAX_MED: 0.0305 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Flufenacet

CHID: 32552 CASRN: 142459-58-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N16

M4ID: 30005682

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	33.6	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.208 MAX_MED: -0.215 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Flumetsulam

CHID: 32615 CASRN: 98967-40-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078016

M4ID: 30005658

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	44.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.45	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.336 MAX_MED: -0.375 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Aldicarb sulfoxide

CHID: 33161 CASRN: 1646-87-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E16

M4ID: 30005898

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	33.82	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.38	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.214 MAX_MED: -0.206 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 17-Methyltestosterone

CHID: 33664 CASRN: 58-18-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A14

M4ID: 30005612

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.27	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.102 MAX_MED: -0.0123 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Haloperidol

CHID: 34150 CASRN: 52-86-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A14

M4ID: 30005996

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	33.03	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0489 MAX_MED: -0.00887 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Icaridin

CHID: 34227 CASRN: 119515-38-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A07

M4ID: 30005619

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.24e-13	1.26	1.21
sd:	1.58e-07	24000	489000

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.95e-12	2.12	1.14	2.38	4.98
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.99	14.99	18.99
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	0.26	0.26	0.26

MAX_MEAN: 0.154 MAX_MED: 0.056 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Fosthiazate
 CHID: 34930 CASRN: 98886-44-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091022
 M4ID: 30005268

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.29e-10	0.603	1.01
sd:	8.94e-06	1210	39000

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.5e-09	0.19	1.47	0.714	5.22
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	51.17	57.17	61.17
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	0.5	0.5	0.5

MAX_MEAN: 0.211 MAX_MED: 0.308 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Citralva

CHID: 36286 CASRN: 5146-66-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F12

M4ID: 30005494

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	23.84	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.33	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.168 MAX_MED: -0.15 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Disodium 4,4'-bis(2-sulfostyryl)biphenyl

CHID: 36467 CASRN: 27344-41-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C12

M4ID: 30005566

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	70.37	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.72	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.256 MAX_MED: -0.201 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Ethyl butyrate

CHID: 40111 CASRN: 105-54-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H02

M4ID: 30005840

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12.48	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0401 MAX_MED: -0.0665 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: (2-Nitro-1-propenyl)benzene

CHID: 41188 CASRN: 705-60-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F04

M4ID: 30005886

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.02	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.25	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0452 MAX_MED: -0.0734 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 5-Ethyl-5-methylhydantoin

CHID: 41368 CASRN: 5394-36-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C16

M4ID: 30005946

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	32.72	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.37	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.235 MAX_MED: -0.205 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: R(-)-Carvone

CHID: 41413 CASRN: 6485-40-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E12

M4ID: 30005518

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	31.75	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.283 MAX_MED: -0.21 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 7-(Dimethylamino)-4-methylcoumarin

CHID: 41422 CASRN: 87-01-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D20

M4ID: 30005918

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	75.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.8	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.087 MAX_MED: -0.0815 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: N,N'-Dibutylthiourea
 CHID: 42187 CASRN: 109-46-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D12
 M4ID: 30005542

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	22.31	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.202 MAX_MED: -0.194 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Butyl lactate

CHID: 42196 CASRN: 138-22-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A01

M4ID: 30006009

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.29e-13	0.929	1.18
sd:	1.32e-07	83600	415000

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.62e-13	1.15	1.43	1.57	4.97
sd:	8.44e-08	275000	411000	210000	1910000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	1.06	7.06	11.06
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	0.23	0.23	0.23

MAX_MEAN: 0.228 MAX_MED: 0.204 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: N-Butyl-p-toluenesulfonamide

CHID: 42198 CASRN: 1907-65-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A16

M4ID: 30005994

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	35.95	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0224 MAX_MED: -0.142 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Sodium 4-methylbenzenesulfonate

CHID: 42415 CASRN: 657-84-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C10

M4ID: 30005952

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	16.15	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.28	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0624 MAX_MED: -0.0688 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Darbufelone mesylate

CHID: 47246 CASRN: 139340-56-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E01

M4ID: 30005529

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	7.14e-12	0.581	1.52
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	6.03e-12	0.615	1.42	1.36	5.42
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-6.54	-0.54	3.46
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	0.21	0.21	0.21

MAX_MEAN: 0.287 MAX_MED: 0.339 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: CP-457920

CHID: 47254 CASRN: 220860-50-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N14

M4ID: 30005684

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	23.09	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.31	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0569 MAX_MED: -0.103 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: PharmaGSID_47263

CHID: 47263 CASRN: 349495-42-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078024

M4ID: 30005650

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	26.17	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.33	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.141 MAX_MED: -0.133 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: CP-863187

CHID: 47294 CASRN: 668981-02-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J14

M4ID: 30005780

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	19.65	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.3	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.0517 MAX_MED: -0.0671 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: MK-812

CHID: 47335 CASRN: 851916-42-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A18

M4ID: 30005608

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12.64	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.27	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.155 MAX_MED: -0.0897 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: SSR180711

CHID: 47359 CASRN: 298198-52-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P24

M4ID: 30005626

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	31.47	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.36	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.208 MAX_MED: -0.2 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: SSR150106
 CHID: 47362 CASRN: NOCAS_47362
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E15
 M4ID: 30005899

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 2.27e-12 1.1 1.23
 sd: NaN NaN NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.51e-12 1.29 1.06 2.05 5.2
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.61	13.61	17.61
PROB:	0.95	0.05	0.01
RMSE:	0.25	0.25	0.25

MAX_MEAN: 0.223 MAX_MED: 0.206 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0.05

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Cyclobutyl phenyl ketone

CHID: 48201 CASRN: 5407-98-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078014

M4ID: 30005660

HILL MODEL: Failed to converge.

GAIN-LOSS MODEL: Failed to converge.

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	38.96	NA	NA
PROB:	1	NA	NA
RMSE:	0.4	NA	NA

MAX_MEAN: -0.273 MAX_MED: -0.31 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 7 ACTP: 0

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 5-Ethylidene-2-norbornene
 CHID: 25306 CASRN: 16219-75-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H22
 M4ID: 30005436

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.344	2.01	6.7
sd:	0.176	0.147	10.9

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.344	2.01	6.7	4.03	3.16
sd:	0.176	0.147	10.9	1490	2830

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	19.38	20.83	24.83
PROB:	0.65	0.31	0.04
RMSE:	0.3	0.28	0.28

MAX_MEAN: 0.313 MAX_MED: 0.428 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 9 ACTP: 0.35

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 7,12-Dimethylbenz(a)anthracene

CHID: 20510 CASRN: 57-97-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E10

M4ID: 30005904

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.361	2.04	8
sd:	0.187	0.207	16.3

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.624	2.08	8	2.33	5.81
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	17.09	19.76	23.73
PROB:	0.77	0.2	0.03
RMSE:	0.29	0.27	0.27

MAX_MEAN: 0.286 MAX_MED: 0.421 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 10 ACTP: 0.23

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Nitrofurantoin
 CHID: 20972 CASRN: 67-20-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H02
 M4ID: 30005456

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.484	1.96	3.96
sd:	19.2	95	793

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.505	1.86	4.11	2.64	3.28
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	4.36	6.22	10.22
PROB:	0.69	0.27	0.04
RMSE:	0.26	0.21	0.21

MAX_MEAN: 0.463 MAX_MED: 0.463 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 10 ACTP: 0.31

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Letrozole

CHID: 23202 CASRN: 112809-51-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K22

M4ID: 30005364

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.622	2.8	0.444
sd:	3.48	7.58	0.72

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.442	2.3	0.447	3.93	4.23
sd:	1.97	6.91	0.728	964	2540

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	24.56	26.24	30.27
PROB:	0.67	0.29	0.04
RMSE:	0.34	0.31	0.31

MAX_MEAN: 0.302 MAX_MED: 0.453 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 10 ACTP: 0.33

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dimethipin

CHID: 24052 CASRN: 55290-64-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K13

M4ID: 30005757

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	6.18e-11	1.73	1.29
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.01	2.26	8	3.74	4.6
sd:	1.6	0.246	10.2	3160	10100

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	12.97	18.97	14.33
PROB:	0.64	0.03	0.32
RMSE:	0.29	0.29	0.24

MAX_MEAN: 0.558 MAX_MED: 0.758 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 10 ACTP: 0.36

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2,2'-(Tetradecylimino)diethanol

CHID: 44865 CASRN: 18924-66-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D10

M4ID: 30005928 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.449	1.96	8
sd:	0.238	0.0926	11.3

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.11	2.01	7.99	2.26	7.49
sd:	2.41	0.171	6.25	0.261	29.8

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	42.43	44.14	47.55
PROB:	0.67	0.28	0.05
RMSE:	0.66	0.57	0.58

MAX_MEAN: 1.18 MAX_MED: 0.553 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 10 ACTP: 0.33

FLAGS: 10; 8

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Sodium benzoate

CHID: 20140 CASRN: 532-32-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K11

M4ID: 30005759

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.252	-2.84	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.252	-2.83	0.3	3.29	8.92
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	18.33	-2.88	1.12
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.3	0.2	0.2

MAX_MEAN: 0.488 MAX_MED: 0.511 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Coumaphos

CHID: 20347 CASRN: 56-72-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K21

M4ID: 30005365

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.237	-3.7	6.17
sd:	0.0586	392	2420

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.237	-3.69	6.27	3.91	10.7
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	31.72	23.54	27.54
PROB:	0.01	0.87	0.12
RMSE:	0.38	0.29	0.29

MAX_MEAN: 0.44 MAX_MED: 0.561 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 0.99

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Thiophanate-methyl

CHID: 24338 CASRN: 23564-05-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I19

M4ID: 30005799

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.147	-3.7	6.11
sd:	0.0399	402	2450

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.147	-3.69	6.2	3.85	17.5
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	10.63	4.5	8.5
PROB:	0.04	0.85	0.11
RMSE:	0.28	0.23	0.23

MAX_MEAN: 0.409 MAX_MED: 0.552 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 0.96

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Methylene bis(thiocyanate)

CHID: 25599 CASRN: 6317-18-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M19

M4ID: 30005703

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.217	-0.893	0.437
sd:	0.103	1.98	0.648

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.263	-0.277	0.334	2.33	17.6
sd:	0.338	4.5	0.634	0.0943	54.8

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.62	-2.71	1.17
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	0.27	0.2	0.2

MAX_MEAN: 0.406 MAX_MED: 0.473 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Diclosulam

CHID: 34528 CASRN: 145701-21-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K23

M4ID: 30005747

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.206	-2.74	4.08
sd:	0.0331	1.91	200

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.206	-2.74	3.94	3.12	10.6
sd:	0.0331	2.15	210	1100	14300

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	14.6	-7.63	-3.63
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.3	0.2	0.2

MAX_MEAN: 0.624 MAX_MED: 0.719 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 8

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1-(6-tert-Butyl-1,1-dimethyl-2,3-dihydro-1H-im

CHID: 44536 CASRN: 13171-00-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M21

M4ID: 30005317

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.262	-2.85	3.46
sd:	0.076	32	739

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.262	-2.87	3.11	3.34	7.55
sd:	0.076	40.4	755	2660	19400

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	41.02	34.55	38.55
PROB:	0.03	0.85	0.12
RMSE:	0.45	0.35	0.35

MAX_MEAN: 0.38 MAX_MED: 0.51 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 13 ACTP: 0.97

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Methyl-2-pentanol
 CHID: 26781 CASRN: 108-11-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H19
 M4ID: 30005823

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.24	1.61	8
sd:	0.0654	0.205	9.95

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.812	1.99	2.67	2.25	15.9
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	0.79	-7.61	-6.44
PROB:	0.01	0.64	0.35
RMSE:	0.24	0.18	0.18

MAX_MEAN: 0.382 MAX_MED: 0.445 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 16 ACTP: 0.99

FLAGS: 12

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Benzo(b)fluoranthene
 CHID: 23907 CASRN: 205-99-2
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I23
 M4ID: 30005411

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.345	-0.938	7.13
sd:	0.054	6.49	752

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.345	-0.938	7.13	3.74	5.59
sd:	0.054	5.84	677	1090	4270

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	23.47	1.62	5.62
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.36	0.2	0.2

MAX_MEAN: 0.555 MAX_MED: 0.514 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Hexamethyldisilazane
 CHID: 25395 CASRN: 999-97-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N23
 M4ID: 30005291

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.407	-0.962	6.54
sd:	0.0447	3.98	686

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.382	-3.7	1.22	4.2	6.28
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	41.09	3.11	3.12
PROB:	0	0.5	0.5
RMSE:	0.44	0.22	0.19

MAX_MEAN: 0.487 MAX_MED: 0.584 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: tert-Nonanethiol

CHID: 27868 CASRN: 25360-10-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K23

M4ID: 30005363

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.377	-2.72	3.44
sd:	0.0497	1.63	256

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.377	-2.72	3.41	2.81	17.7
sd:	0.0497	1.67	259	408	12900

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	29.96	2.14	6.14
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.45	0.22	0.22

MAX_MEAN: 0.713 MAX_MED: 0.648 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 12; 8

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Glyceryl monoricinoleate

CHID: 42007 CASRN: 1323-38-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M07

M4ID: 30005715

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.401	2.07	8
sd:	0.0968	0.144	12.3

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.401	2.07	8	3.2	6.74
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-21.76	-26.61	-22.61
PROB:	0.07	0.82	0.11
RMSE:	0.17	0.14	0.14

MAX_MEAN: 0.313 MAX_MED: 0.428 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 20 ACTP: 0.93

FLAGS: 12

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Propyl gallate
 CHID: 21201 CASRN: 121-79-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B12
 M4ID: 30005974

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.393	2.05	8
sd:	0.117	0.12	10.2

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.602	2.08	8	2.33	8.33
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.45	1.89	5.87
PROB:	0.13	0.77	0.1
RMSE:	0.24	0.2	0.2

MAX_MEAN: 0.381 MAX_MED: 0.427 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 21 ACTP: 0.87

FLAGS: 12

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Phenyl salicylate

CHID: 21957 CASRN: 118-55-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L19

M4ID: 30005727

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.228	-3.69	6.71
sd:	0.036	375	2530

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.289	-3.07	3.25	1.98	2.63
sd:	0.0451	31.4	271	0.165	2.59

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	17.53	-4.76	-7.07
PROB:	0	0.24	0.76
RMSE:	0.3	0.19	0.17

MAX_MEAN: 0.33 MAX_MED: 0.462 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 0 FITC: 24 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Pyrene

CHID: 24289 CASRN: 129-00-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M23

M4ID: 30005315

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.424	-3.7	1.14
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.424	-3.7	1.14	3.47	14.1
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	46.73	-11.23	-7.23
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.48	0.18	0.18

MAX_MEAN: 0.628 MAX_MED: 0.555 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 36 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2,3,6-Trimethylphenol

CHID: 22187 CASRN: 2416-94-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G11

M4ID: 30005855

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.459	2.04	8
sd:	0.0811	0.0565	7.55

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.667	2.07	8	2.34	10.1
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-19.57	-28.37	-24.4
PROB:	0.01	0.87	0.12
RMSE:	0.18	0.14	0.14

MAX_MEAN: 0.346 MAX_MED: 0.449 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 37 ACTP: 0.99

FLAGS: 11; 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Prallethrin

CHID: 32572 CASRN: 23031-36-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078019

M4ID: 30005655

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.467	1.98	8
sd:	0.144	0.0577	7.82

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.995	2.04	7.81	2.29	12
sd:	1.28	0.126	6.49	0.0671	129

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.88	-0.73	2.72
PROB:	0.03	0.82	0.15
RMSE:	0.27	0.2	0.2

MAX_MEAN: 0.47 MAX_MED: 0.433 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 37 ACTP: 0.97

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: (4Z)-4-Decenal
 CHID: 41514 CASRN: 21662-09-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K09
 M4ID: 30005761

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.446	1.61	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.596	2.3	0.3	4.29	18
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.12	-8.85	-5.07
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	0.27	0.17	0.17

MAX_MEAN: 0.566 MAX_MED: 0.549 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 38 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11; 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Amino-5-azotoluene
 CHID: 20069 CASRN: 97-56-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078F22
 M4ID: 30005868

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 1.27 1.96 8
 sd: 0.0836 0.015 3.06

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.66 1.99 8 2.37 6.92
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	40.23	-19.8	-17.07
PROB:	0	0.8	0.2
RMSE:	0.51	0.14	0.14

MAX_MEAN: 1.25 MAX_MED: 1.23 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: tert-Butylhydroquinone
 CHID: 20220 CASRN: 1948-33-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C21
 M4ID: 30005941

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.925	2.02	5.96
sd:	0.102	0.0379	3.1

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.22	2.06	5.33	2.33	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.63	-27.68	-23.77
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.32	0.14	0.14

MAX_MEAN: 0.806 MAX_MED: 0.904 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: o,p'-DDD

CHID: 20372 CASRN: 53-19-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K19

M4ID: 30005751

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.797	2.01	8
sd:	0.121	0.062	9.68

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.797	2.01	8	4.24	17.6
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	27.52	10.69	14.69
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.37	0.24	0.24

MAX_MEAN: 0.792 MAX_MED: 0.739 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dichlone

CHID: 20425 CASRN: 117-80-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078E09

M4ID: 30005905

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.797	2.04	8
sd:	0.0957	0.0459	4.84

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1	2.05	8	2.47	3.49
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	19.71	-1.48	2.44
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.33	0.19	0.19

MAX_MEAN: 0.788 MAX_MED: 0.79 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 17alpha-Ethinylestradiol

CHID: 20576 CASRN: 57-63-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J08

M4ID: 30005402

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.889	1.89	5.49
sd:	0.109	0.0412	2.08

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.889	1.89	5.49	4.18	8.63
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	37.21	-8.39	-4.39
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.44	0.18	0.18

MAX_MEAN: 0.914 MAX_MED: 0.839 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: FD&C Green No. 3
 CHID: 20673 CASRN: 2353-45-9
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N22
 M4ID: 30005676

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.593	1.97	6.61
sd:	0.0575	0.0245	3.19

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.771	2	5.87	2.53	2.38
sd:	1.02	0.147	4.09	1.73	19.6

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.44	-36.07	-32.1
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.25	0.11	0.11

MAX_MEAN: 0.587 MAX_MED: 0.6 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Hexylresorcinol

CHID: 20699 CASRN: 136-77-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A03

M4ID: 30005623

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.783	1.95	8
sd:	0.129	0.0402	4.31

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.783	1.95	8	4.04	4.32
sd:	0.129	0.0402	4.31	3070	7730

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	27.95	5.6	9.6
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.38	0.23	0.23

MAX_MEAN: 0.767 MAX_MED: 0.833 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2,2'-Methylenebis(4-methyl-6-tert-butylphenol)

CHID: 20870 CASRN: 119-47-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P16

M4ID: 30005634

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.01	1.67	5.16
sd:	0.2	0.052	2.99

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.01	1.67	5.16	3.81	16.7
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	122.48	54.59	58.59
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	1.77	0.51	0.51

MAX_MEAN: 3.06 MAX_MED: 3.07 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Triphenyltin hydroxide

CHID: 21409 CASRN: 76-87-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I21

M4ID: 30005797

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.76	0.871	2.46
sd:	0.0822	0.0765	0.654

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.76	0.871	2.46	3.91	5.12
sd:	0.0822	0.0765	0.654	1590	5000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	148.59	52.58	56.58
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	2.62	0.82	0.82

MAX_MEAN: 3.83 MAX_MED: 3.82 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Ziram

CHID: 21464 CASRN: 137-30-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A08

M4ID: 30006002 BRK

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.67	1.29	8
sd:	0.118	0.0301	18.7

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.67	1.29	8	3.85	5.33
sd:	0.118	0.0301	18.7	942	3260

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	104.03	43.04	47.04
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	1.36	0.56	0.56

MAX_MEAN: 3.04 MAX_MED: 3.48 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Octadecanoic acid

CHID: 21642 CASRN: 57-11-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K07

M4ID: 30005379

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.516	1.98	6.75
sd:	0.133	0.0768	12.1

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.516	1.98	6.75	4.05	3.74
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	23.64	15.95	19.95
PROB:	0.02	0.86	0.12
RMSE:	0.33	0.27	0.27

MAX_MEAN: 0.509 MAX_MED: 0.557 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 0.98

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Dodecylphenol

CHID: 22508 CASRN: 104-43-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A11

M4ID: 30005615

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.04	1.86	8
sd:	0.297	0.028	3.2

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.04	1.86	8	3.96	5
sd:	0.297	0.028	3.2	2180	6620

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	97.44	57.28	61.28
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	1.35	0.68	0.68

MAX_MEAN: 2.76 MAX_MED: 3.12 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Tetracycline
 CHID: 23645 CASRN: 60-54-8
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C11
 M4ID: 30005951

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.549	1.99	7.63
sd:	0.0544	0.0214	4.15

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.807	2.04	6.57	2.36	6.15
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-7.48	-45.95	-41.95
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.22	0.1	0.1

MAX_MEAN: 0.562 MAX_MED: 0.509 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Propargite

CHID: 24276 CASRN: 2312-35-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D06

M4ID: 30005548

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.552	1.16	3.01
sd:	0.0532	0.131	1.96

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.552	1.16	3.01	4.28	4.35
sd:	0.0532	0.131	1.96	2000	4430

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	36.18	-10.44	-6.44
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.4	0.17	0.17

MAX_MEAN: 0.68 MAX_MED: 0.703 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Isoproterenol hydrochloride

CHID: 25486 CASRN: 51-30-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H10

M4ID: 30005832

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.882	1.95	4.09
sd:	0.156	0.057	2.79

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.34	2.03	3.62	2.33	10.5
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	32.27	-0.62	3.06
PROB:	0	0.86	0.14
RMSE:	0.41	0.2	0.2

MAX_MEAN: 0.873 MAX_MED: 0.761 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Sodium dodecyl sulfate
 CHID: 26031 CASRN: 151-21-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H22
 M4ID: 30005820

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.63	2.01	8
sd:	0.112	0.0122	1.49

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.63	2.01	8	4.29	14.1
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	76.95	10.48	14.48
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	1.15	0.36	0.36

MAX_MEAN: 3.11 MAX_MED: 3.6 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dibutyltin dichloride

CHID: 27292 CASRN: 683-18-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H06

M4ID: 30005452

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.47	1.05	1.85
sd:	0.0495	0.0215	0.147

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.47	1.05	1.85	3.85	6.68
sd:	0.0495	0.0215	0.147	5190	22500

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	142.4	-25.77	-21.77
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	2.35	0.13	0.13

MAX_MEAN: 3.49 MAX_MED: 3.51 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2,4-Bis(1-methyl-1-phenylethyl)phenol

CHID: 29241 CASRN: 2772-45-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J04

M4ID: 30005406

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.14	1.88	5.65
sd:	0.218	0.0374	1.65

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.04	1.96	8	2.33	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	99.78	37.26	37.71
PROB:	0	0.56	0.44
RMSE:	1.37	0.41	0.36

MAX_MEAN: 2.92 MAX_MED: 3.08 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Sodium lauryl polyoxyethylene ether sulfat

CHID: 29298 CASRN: 9004-82-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J21

M4ID: 30005773

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.93	2.03	6.19
sd:	0.117	0.014	1.03

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.76	2.05	5.77	2.4	7.41
sd:	1.92	0.0346	1.08	0.0161	11.7

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	84.26	3.02	6.78
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	1.33	0.25	0.25

MAX_MEAN: 3.86 MAX_MED: 3.86 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Perfluorononanoic acid
 CHID: 31863 CASRN: 375-95-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C02
 M4ID: 30005576

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.926	2.02	5.74
sd:	0.116	0.0503	3.05

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.926	2.02	5.74	3.4	5.43
sd:	0.116	0.0503	3.05	1610	8090

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.72	-1.29	2.71
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.31	0.29	0.29

MAX_MEAN: 0.484 MAX_MED: 0.911 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Chlorhexidine diacetate
 CHID: 32345 CASRN: 56-95-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J10
 M4ID: 30005400

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 3.92 1.79 6.27
 sd: 0.0911 0.0109 0.63

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 3.92 1.79 6.27 2.96 13.1
 sd: 0.0911 0.0109 0.63 1220 24200

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	127.62	-5.29	-1.29
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	2.03	0.19	0.19

MAX_MEAN: 3.91 MAX_MED: 3.97 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Pyraclostrobin
 CHID: 32638 CASRN: 175013-18-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L24
 M4ID: 30005338

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.804	0.364	0.83
sd:	0.0975	0.204	0.474

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.804	0.364	0.83	3.67	6.19
sd:	0.0975	0.204	0.474	1100	5030

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	63.6	-8.41	-4.41
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.62	0.19	0.19

MAX_MEAN: 0.877 MAX_MED: 0.899 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Nonylphenol

CHID: 33836 CASRN: 104-40-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F10

M4ID: 30005496

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.17	2	8
sd:	0.169	0.028	3.98

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.3	2.01	8	2.35	18
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	43.26	16.45	20.44
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.5	0.27	0.27

MAX_MEAN: 1.19 MAX_MED: 1.15 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Tebufenpyrad

CHID: 34223 CASRN: 119168-77-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G06

M4ID: 30005476

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.518	0.22	1.08
sd:	0.0676	0.298	0.499

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.518	0.22	1.08	4.29	8.95
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	40.45	-14.39	-10.39
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.43	0.16	0.16

MAX_MEAN: 0.583 MAX_MED: 0.636 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Metconazole
 CHID: 34497 CASRN: 125116-23-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078011
 M4ID: 30005663

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 0.7 1.98 8
 sd: 0.127 0.0328 4.35

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 1.21 2.03 8 2.31 11.2
 sd: NaN NaN NaN NaN NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	21	0.36	3.46
PROB:	0	0.83	0.17
RMSE:	0.34	0.2	0.2

MAX_MEAN: 0.716 MAX_MED: 0.602 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Ethofumesate
 CHID: 34580 CASRN: 26225-79-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K17
 M4ID: 30005369

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.938	1.97	6.1
sd:	0.104	0.0268	3.55

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.34	2.03	4.83	2.34	11.7
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	28.52	-10.34	-6.46
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	0.39	0.17	0.17

MAX_MEAN: 0.942 MAX_MED: 0.86 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Hexaconazole

CHID: 34653 CASRN: 79983-71-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078003

M4ID: 30005671

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.798	2	8
sd:	0.121	0.0337	4.02

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.05	2.02	8	2.4	4.84
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	21.19	1.53	4.99
PROB:	0	0.85	0.15
RMSE:	0.34	0.2	0.2

MAX_MEAN: 0.732 MAX_MED: 0.866 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Methylbenzethonium chloride

CHID: 35708 CASRN: 25155-18-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091D10

M4ID: 30005544

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.58	1.62	7.44
sd:	0.0663	0.0309	2.93

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.58	1.62	7.44	3.18	10.9
sd:	0.0663	0.0309	2.93	1840	22700

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	134.21	4.51	8.51
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	2.15	0.22	0.22

MAX_MEAN: 3.63 MAX_MED: 3.59 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,4-Dihydroxy-2-naphthoic acid

CHID: 37730 CASRN: 31519-22-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L09

M4ID: 30005737

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.25	1.51	2.49
sd:	0.106	0.0251	0.289

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.22	1.55	2.28	4.22	0.331
sd:	2.41	0.052	0.336	2.69	0.804

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	143.65	7.39	10.87
PROB:	0	0.85	0.15
RMSE:	2.48	0.35	0.35

MAX_MEAN: 4.17 MAX_MED: 4.18 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Methoxy-4-nitroaniline

CHID: 38700 CASRN: 97-52-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G09

M4ID: 30005857

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.42	1.97	5.31
sd:	0.0935	0.0189	1.98

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.83	2.02	4.5	2.35	13.5
sd:	1.04	0.0916	1.29	0.0218	21.6

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	43.39	-30.47	-27.34
PROB:	0	0.83	0.17
RMSE:	0.55	0.12	0.12

MAX_MEAN: 1.39 MAX_MED: 1.39 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dinocap

CHID: 40352 CASRN: 39300-45-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E22

M4ID: 30005508

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.593	0.911	3.71
sd:	0.073	0.142	4.75

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.593	0.911	3.71	3.52	6.8
sd:	0.073	0.142	4.75	1650	9240

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	50.88	13.9	17.9
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.51	0.25	0.25

MAX_MEAN: 0.718 MAX_MED: 0.676 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Diniconazole

CHID: 40363 CASRN: 83657-24-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C06

M4ID: 30005572

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.17	2.06	5.23
sd:	0.288	0.0433	1.66

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.84	2.06	5.23	4.3	0.343
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	73.68	12.89	16.89
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	1.04	0.25	0.25

MAX_MEAN: 2.93 MAX_MED: 3.07 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2,2',4,4'-Tetrahydroxybenzophenone

CHID: 41306 CASRN: 131-55-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091F11

M4ID: 30005495

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.507	1.97	8
sd:	0.111	0.0421	5.89

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.823	2.01	8	2.32	10
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	15.96	4.23	7.52
PROB:	0	0.84	0.16
RMSE:	0.29	0.22	0.21

MAX_MEAN: 0.489 MAX_MED: 0.433 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11; 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Bromophenol blue

CHID: 41682 CASRN: 115-39-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C02

M4ID: 30005960

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.632	2.04	7.89
sd:	0.0847	0.0583	7.32

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.632	2.04	7.89	3.49	5.46
sd:	0.0848	0.0583	7.32	2750	12800

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.73	-9.11	-5.11
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.28	0.18	0.18

MAX_MEAN: 0.627 MAX_MED: 0.62 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Oleyl sarcosine

CHID: 42243 CASRN: 110-25-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I11

M4ID: 30005423

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.782	1.98	8
sd:	0.114	0.0277	3.61

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.22	2.03	6.86	2.32	13.1
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	19.17	-12.48	-8.51
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.34	0.17	0.17

MAX_MEAN: 0.784 MAX_MED: 0.772 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Sodium tridecyl sulfate

CHID: 42418 CASRN: 3026-63-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078P04

M4ID: 30005646

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.38	2.06	8
sd:	0.178	0.0354	3.23

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.12	2.08	8	2.44	4.7
sd:	4.47	0.0729	3.17	0.129	20.5

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	75.09	22.11	26.05
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	1.13	0.28	0.28

MAX_MEAN: 3.34 MAX_MED: 3.4 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Methyltriethylammonium chloride

CHID: 44487 CASRN: 5137-55-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078A09

M4ID: 30006001

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.53	1.61	4.05
sd:	0.0816	0.0205	0.562

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.53	1.61	4.05	3.48	7.89
sd:	0.0816	0.0205	0.562	1640	11000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	127.51	14.06	18.06
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	1.97	0.44	0.44

MAX_MEAN: 3.64 MAX_MED: 3.52 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: SR271425

CHID: 47347 CASRN: 155990-20-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J04

M4ID: 30005790

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.994	1.98	4.47
sd:	0.15	0.0583	2.61

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.994	1.98	4.47	4.29	3.35
sd:	0.15	0.0583	2.61	2240	3890

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	37.38	9.04	13.04
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.43	0.23	0.23

MAX_MEAN: 0.961 MAX_MED: 0.974 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4-Butylphenol

CHID: 47425 CASRN: 1638-22-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M09

M4ID: 30005713

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.68	2.03	8
sd:	0.0806	0.0345	3.95

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.945	2.05	8	2.36	6.5
sd:	1.38	0.11	3.63	0.288	17.8

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	2.61	-23.96	-20.23
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	0.26	0.14	0.14

MAX_MEAN: 0.66 MAX_MED: 0.686 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Acid Yellow 11

CHID: 47451 CASRN: 6359-82-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A13

M4ID: 30005613

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.567	2.05	8
sd:	0.0737	0.0486	5.42

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.792	2.07	8	2.4	4.14
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-5.59	-28.57	-24.6
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.23	0.13	0.13

MAX_MEAN: 0.556 MAX_MED: 0.573 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 4,4'-Sulfonylbis[2-(prop-2-en-1-yl)phenol]

CHID: 47598 CASRN: 41481-66-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I05

M4ID: 30005429

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.714	2.13	8
sd:	0.35	0.358	14.2

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.714	2.13	8	4.03	5.76
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	9.98	-7.26	-3.26
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.29	0.18	0.18

MAX_MEAN: 0.686 MAX_MED: 0.69 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: PharmaGSID_48505

CHID: 48505 CASRN: NOCAS_48505

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078007

M4ID: 30005667

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.622	2.03	8
sd:	0.0851	0.046	5.89

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.817	2.05	8	2.36	8.94
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	11.79	-6.34	-2.4
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.28	0.19	0.19

MAX_MEAN: 0.615 MAX_MED: 0.632 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 41 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Auramine hydrochloride
CHID: 20114 CASRN: 2465-27-2
SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J09
M4ID: 30005785

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.25	1.99	1.36
sd:	0.371	0.224	0.432

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.25	1.99	1.36	4.18	3.97
sd:	0.374	0.225	0.438	1260	2620

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	32.47	-23.48	-19.48
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.42	0.14	0.14

MAX_MEAN: 0.914 MAX_MED: 0.935 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Azinphos-methyl

CHID: 20122 CASRN: 86-50-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078B19

M4ID: 30005967

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.531	1.81	1.51
sd:	0.208	0.273	0.755

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.776	2.02	1.39	2.34	11.6
sd:	0.605	0.451	0.59	0.0731	22.1

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	5.98	-29.48	-26.25
PROB:	0	0.83	0.17
RMSE:	0.26	0.13	0.13

MAX_MEAN: 0.436 MAX_MED: 0.463 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11; 7

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Catechol

CHID: 20257 CASRN: 120-80-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M18

M4ID: 30005320

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.753	1.99	2.47
sd:	0.298	0.185	1.54

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.753	1.99	2.47	4.09	3.33
sd:	0.298	0.185	1.54	819	1590

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	18.64	-8.58	-4.58
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.33	0.18	0.18

MAX_MEAN: 0.73 MAX_MED: 0.582 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane

CHID: 20375 CASRN: 50-29-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E17

M4ID: 30005513

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.93	2.38	8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.1	2.3	8	4.09	15
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	19.64	14.27	18.28
PROB:	0.06	0.83	0.11
RMSE:	0.5	0.39	0.39

MAX_MEAN: 1.15 MAX_MED: 0.531 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 0.94

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Methoxy-5-nitroaniline

CHID: 20943 CASRN: 99-59-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I11

M4ID: 30005807

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.959	2.1	2.05
sd:	0.672	0.359	1.54

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.03	2.11	2.13	2.36	17.8
sd:	0.906	0.372	1.46	0.00685	13.9

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	10.01	-27.84	-23.87
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.32	0.13	0.13

MAX_MEAN: 0.796 MAX_MED: 0.689 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Quercetin

CHID: 21218 CASRN: 117-39-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H15

M4ID: 30005827

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.688	2.11	2.78
sd:	0.374	0.219	2.57

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.688	2.11	2.78	3.86	4.93
sd:	0.375	0.219	2.57	1500	4770

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.67	-6.57	-2.57
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.26	0.18	0.18

MAX_MEAN: 0.555 MAX_MED: 0.565 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Retinol acetate

CHID: 21240 CASRN: 127-47-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078G05

M4ID: 30005861

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.625	2.19	4.8
sd:	0.74	0.354	5.3

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.625	2.19	4.8	3	8.82
sd:	0.74	0.354	5.3	1150	14700

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-8.27	-23.98	-19.98
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.21	0.15	0.15

MAX_MEAN: 0.476 MAX_MED: 0.533 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Rifampicin

CHID: 21244 CASRN: 13292-46-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P17

M4ID: 30005249

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.27	1.7	1.13
sd:	0.469	0.195	0.272

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.99	1.92	1.02	2.34	17.3
sd:	1.52	0.421	0.258	0.015	14

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	91.5	9.94	12.85
PROB:	0	0.81	0.19
RMSE:	1.06	0.24	0.24

MAX_MEAN: 1.97 MAX_MED: 1.79 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Sulfasalazine

CHID: 21256 CASRN: 599-79-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M05

M4ID: 30005717

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.4	2.18	1.9
sd:	1.83	0.387	1.11

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.4	2.17	1.96	2.49	8.63
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	53.09	-2.92	1.07
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.63	0.2	0.2

MAX_MEAN: 1.61 MAX_MED: 1.46 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: FD&C Yellow 5

CHID: 21455 CASRN: 1934-21-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C18

M4ID: 30005560

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.04	2.07	1.74
sd:	0.862	0.246	0.765

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.04	2.07	1.74	3.81	6.98
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	59.15	8.29	12.29
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.64	0.23	0.23

MAX_MEAN: 1.48 MAX_MED: 1.4 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2,2',6,6'-Tetrachlorobisphenol A

CHID: 21770 CASRN: 79-95-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K15

M4ID: 30005755

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.4	2.15	3.67
sd:	1.64	0.176	2.02

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.4	2.15	3.67	3.86	4.06
sd:	1.64	0.176	2.02	2660	7330

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	61.41	6.48	10.48
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.95	0.24	0.24

MAX_MEAN: 2.81 MAX_MED: 2.68 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 3-Trifluoromethyl-4-nitrophenol

CHID: 21788 CASRN: 88-30-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091023

M4ID: 30005267

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.96	2.28	0.67
sd:	1.3	0.513	0.223

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.96	2.28	0.67	3.21	10.1
sd:	1.3	0.513	0.223	1520	16900

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	81.65	35.32	39.32
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.91	0.38	0.38

MAX_MEAN: 1.92 MAX_MED: 1.83 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 3,4-Dichloroaniline
 CHID: 21815 CASRN: 95-76-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L22
 M4ID: 30005340

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.15	2.33	2.21
sd:	2.51	0.822	2.74

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.08	2.3	2.3	3.63	11
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	35.82	35.09	39.1
PROB:	0.38	0.55	0.07
RMSE:	0.41	0.37	0.37

MAX_MEAN: 0.527 MAX_MED: 0.68 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 0.62

FLAGS: 16; 11; 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Propanil

CHID: 22111 CASRN: 709-98-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N24

M4ID: 30005290

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.1	2.28	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.801	1.39	0.3	3.76	17.2
sd:	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	41.45	1.58	5.82
PROB:	0	0.89	0.11
RMSE:	0.44	0.21	0.21

MAX_MEAN: 0.626 MAX_MED: 0.62 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Bromoxynil

CHID: 22162 CASRN: 1689-84-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E21

M4ID: 30005509

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.64	2.11	6.17
sd:	0.395	0.31	12.6

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.64	2.11	6.17	3.65	5.02
sd:	0.395	0.31	12.6	10900	42100

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	11.24	1.17	5.17
PROB:	0.01	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.28	0.2	0.2

MAX_MEAN: 0.597 MAX_MED: 0.621 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 0.99

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Bisphenol B

CHID: 22442 CASRN: 77-40-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091P10

M4ID: 30005256

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.17	2.23	4.89
sd:	6.23	0.685	8.21

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.17	2.23	4.89	4.08	3.31
sd:	6.28	0.69	8.27	1450	2770

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	50.03	31.58	35.58
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.58	0.33	0.33

MAX_MEAN: 1.49 MAX_MED: 1.44 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Acetochlor

CHID: 23848 CASRN: 34256-82-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E24

M4ID: 30005506

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.737	2.13	2.15
sd:	0.53	0.339	1.47

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.737	2.13	2.15	3.57	5.74
sd:	0.53	0.339	1.47	1340	6100

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.29	-7.99	-3.99
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.26	0.18	0.18

MAX_MEAN: 0.513 MAX_MED: 0.574 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Cyromazine

CHID: 23999 CASRN: 66215-27-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091007

M4ID: 30005283

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.809	2.29	5.24
sd:	5.83	1.23	20

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.809	2.29	5.24	4.3	2.25
sd:	5.8	1.23	19.9	785	917

	CNST	HILL	GMLS
AIC:	11.31	10.13	14.13
PROB:	0.33	0.59	0.08
RMSE:	0.28	0.25	0.25

MAX_MEAN: 0.419 MAX_MED: 0.433 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 0.67

FLAGS: 16; 11; 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2,4,5-Trichlorophenol
 CHID: 24359 CASRN: 95-95-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J22
 M4ID: 30005388

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.829	1.94	1.75
sd:	0.512	0.396	1.44

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.829	1.94	1.75	3.53	5.82
sd:	0.512	0.396	1.44	1580	7620

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	35.09	16.04	20.04
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.41	0.26	0.26

MAX_MEAN: 0.688 MAX_MED: 0.645 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Colchicine

CHID: 24845 CASRN: 64-86-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J06

M4ID: 30005404

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.895	1.98	0.387
sd:	1.09	2.73	0.241

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.895	1.98	0.387	3.81	5.67
sd:	1.09	2.73	0.241	1610	6060

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	28.78	-30.46	-26.46
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.35	0.13	0.13

MAX_MEAN: 0.622 MAX_MED: 0.545 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Cycloheximide

CHID: 24882 CASRN: 66-81-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078D09

M4ID: 30005929

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.705	1.23	0.772
sd:	0.333	0.735	0.526

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.705	1.23	0.772	3.75	5.06
sd:	0.333	0.735	0.526	1490	5080

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	40.52	-0.56	3.44
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.43	0.19	0.19

MAX_MEAN: 0.653 MAX_MED: 0.732 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Nitroaniline

CHID: 25726 CASRN: 88-74-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N01

M4ID: 30005313

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.908	2.21	1.73
sd:	2.73	1.64	3.55

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.908	2.21	1.73	3.62	4.67
sd:	2.74	1.65	3.56	802	2920

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	15.66	1.87	5.87
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.3	0.21	0.21

MAX_MEAN: 0.549 MAX_MED: 0.519 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Octhilinone
 CHID: 25805 CASRN: 26530-20-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L06
 M4ID: 30005356

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 3.26 2.23 7.84
 sd: 0.603 0.0382 2.1

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 3.26 2.24 8 4.01 4.58
 sd: 0.621 0.0383 2.28 1820 4880

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	38.11	-8.2	-4.3
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.8	0.18	0.18

MAX_MEAN: 2.45 MAX_MED: 2.53 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,10-Phenanthroline
 CHID: 25857 CASRN: 66-71-7
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H18
 M4ID: 30005440

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.24	1.53	0.95
sd:	0.27	0.266	0.226

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.24	1.53	0.95	3.67	6.41
sd:	0.27	0.266	0.226	1670	7820

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	60.93	-29.7	-25.7
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.61	0.12	0.12

MAX_MEAN: 1.08 MAX_MED: 1.15 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Triclocarban

CHID: 26214 CASRN: 101-20-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L21

M4ID: 30005341

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.64	2.3	0.3
sd:	2.73	4.62	0.282

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.64	2.3	0.3	2.74	5.17
sd:	2.84	4.62	0.265	23.8	235

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	66.49	27.54	31.54
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.67	0.32	0.32

MAX_MEAN: 0.86 MAX_MED: 0.703 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Triglycidyl isocyanurate

CHID: 26262 CASRN: 2451-62-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I06

M4ID: 30005428

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.32	2.23	2.09
sd:	0.555	0.181	0.694

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.32	2.23	2.09	3.55	6.9
sd:	0.555	0.181	0.694	1860	10300

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	7.6	-33.13	-29.13
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.31	0.12	0.12

MAX_MEAN: 0.84 MAX_MED: 0.84 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2-Tert-Butyl-5-methylphenol

CHID: 26529 CASRN: 88-60-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C05

M4ID: 30005573

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.564	2.24	8
sd:	0.376	0.121	4.5

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.564	2.24	8	4.3	3.04
sd:	0.373	0.12	4.49	571	874

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.71	-29.66	-25.66
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.18	0.12	0.12

MAX_MEAN: 0.424 MAX_MED: 0.428 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11; 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Calcium dodecylbenzene sulfonate

CHID: 27891 CASRN: 26264-06-2

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G13

M4ID: 30005469

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.586	2.25	8
sd:	2.93	0.746	34.9

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.586	2.25	7.99	4.05	1.94
sd:	2.83	0.722	34	284	317

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	4.13	-0.89	3.11
PROB:	0.07	0.82	0.11
RMSE:	0.24	0.2	0.2

MAX_MEAN: 0.411 MAX_MED: 0.445 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 0.93

FLAGS: 11; 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dodecylphenol

CHID: 27926 CASRN: 27193-86-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091B19

M4ID: 30005583

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.6	2.15	3.63
sd:	1.05	0.106	1.28

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	3.6	2.15	3.62	3.79	5.08
sd:	1.06	0.108	1.29	896	3070

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	61.52	45.87	49.87
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.91	0.66	0.66

MAX_MEAN: 1.91 MAX_MED: 2.81 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 3-Iodo-2-propynyl-N-butylcarbamate

CHID: 28038 CASRN: 55406-53-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M23

M4ID: 30005699

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.71	2.13	3.52
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.71	2.13	3.52	3.93	3.93
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	89.02	23.64	27.64
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	1.35	0.35	0.35

MAX_MEAN: 3.72 MAX_MED: 3.85 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Sodium persulfate

CHID: 29698 CASRN: 7775-27-1

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M07

M4ID: 30005331

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.865	2.32	1.75
sd:	3.92	2.22	4.16

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.84	2.3	1.79	4.15	2.74
sd:	5.22	3.01	5.8	655	1010

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	17.89	16.98	20.98
PROB:	0.36	0.56	0.08
RMSE:	0.31	0.27	0.27

MAX_MEAN: 0.375 MAX_MED: 0.542 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 0.64

FLAGS: 16; 11; 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Bifenazate

CHID: 32525 CASRN: 149877-41-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G22

M4ID: 30005460

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.925	1.81	2.53
sd:	0.264	0.127	2.13

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.36	1.97	1.92	2.35	10.8
sd:	2.27	0.74	1.89	0.132	34.5

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	47.57	17.12	20.95
PROB:	0	0.87	0.13
RMSE:	0.5	0.27	0.27

MAX_MEAN: 0.848 MAX_MED: 0.868 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Fenpyroximate (Z,E)

CHID: 32550 CASRN: 111812-58-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E11

M4ID: 30005519

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.906	2.25	1.78
sd:	0.898	0.507	1.49

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.906	2.25	1.78	4.01	4.56
sd:	0.898	0.507	1.49	2220	5970

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	17.79	6.09	10.09
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.3	0.23	0.23

MAX_MEAN: 0.542 MAX_MED: 0.514 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Fluazinam

CHID: 32551 CASRN: 79622-59-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091A01

M4ID: 30005625

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.71	2.22	0.927
sd:	1.31	0.563	0.385

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.71	2.22	0.927	4.06	4.55
sd:	1.31	0.563	0.385	1380	3580

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	40.62	14.67	18.67
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.49	0.26	0.26

MAX_MEAN: 1.03 MAX_MED: 1.2 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Pyridaben

CHID: 32573 CASRN: 96489-71-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M09

M4ID: 30005329

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.701	0.947	0.5
sd:	0.603	1.92	0.533

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.701	0.947	0.5	4.25	5.27
sd:	0.603	1.92	0.533	36700	99100

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	51.03	24.85	28.85
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.53	0.31	0.31

MAX_MEAN: 0.651 MAX_MED: 0.624 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Trifloxystrobin

CHID: 32580 CASRN: 141517-21-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J24

M4ID: 30005386

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.685	1.5	0.514
sd:	0.286	0.787	0.235

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.685	1.49	0.522	2.41	16.4
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	22.8	-54.41	-50.44
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.32	0.08	0.08

MAX_MEAN: 0.492 MAX_MED: 0.493 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 11

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Z-Tetrachlorvinphos

CHID: 32648 CASRN: 22248-79-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N21

M4ID: 30005293

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.87	2.75	0.558
sd:	3.66	2.56	0.472

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.34	2.3	0.634	4.17	3.33
sd:	2.32	2.13	0.529	566	1000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	55.01	43.71	47.8
PROB:	0	0.88	0.11
RMSE:	0.59	0.43	0.43

MAX_MEAN: 0.874 MAX_MED: 0.604 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Fluoxastrobin

CHID: 34625 CASRN: 361377-29-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078J05

M4ID: 30005789

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.14	1.58	1.25
sd:	0.126	0.117	0.222

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.14	1.58	1.25	3.7	5.98
sd:	0.126	0.117	0.222	1150	4940

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	57.66	-30.95	-26.95
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.58	0.14	0.14

MAX_MEAN: 1.03 MAX_MED: 1.04 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Disiquonium chloride

CHID: 35589 CASRN: 68959-20-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J17

M4ID: 30005393

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.787	2	0.68
sd:	0.316	0.509	0.342

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.787	2	0.68	3.85	5.45
sd:	0.316	0.509	0.342	1640	5760

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	18.12	-20.54	-16.54
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.3	0.14	0.14

MAX_MEAN: 0.561 MAX_MED: 0.592 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Sodium decyl sulfate
 CHID: 36229 CASRN: 142-87-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091H23
 M4ID: 30005435

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.759	1.75	0.339
sd:	0.327	1.08	0.144

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.759	1.75	0.337	3.58	6.58
sd:	0.33	1.09	0.14	935	4810

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	17.2	-18.6	-14.6
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.32	0.14	0.14

MAX_MEAN: 0.58 MAX_MED: 0.587 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Amiodarone hydrochloride

CHID: 37185 CASRN: 19774-82-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091017

M4ID: 30005273

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.14	2.23	1.97
sd:	1.11	0.235	0.782

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.14	2.23	1.97	4.13	4.31
sd:	1.1	0.233	0.774	1600	3800

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	39.41	11.44	15.44
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.5	0.27	0.27

MAX_MEAN: 1.17 MAX_MED: 1.29 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Potassium perfluorooctanesulfonate

CHID: 37706 CASRN: 2795-39-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E06

M4ID: 30005524

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.78	2.14	3.27
sd:	1.11	0.233	2.3

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.78	2.14	3.27	3.46	5.92
sd:	1.11	0.233	2.3	1760	9190

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	36.01	22.42	26.42
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.48	0.34	0.34

MAX_MEAN: 1 MAX_MED: 1.33 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 5-Chlorosalicylanilide
 CHID: 37749 CASRN: 4638-48-6
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091I21
 M4ID: 30005413

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.34	2.21	0.532
sd:	1.38	1.57	0.288

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.34	2.21	0.532	3.5	6.87
sd:	1.38	1.57	0.288	1430	8210

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	46.99	18.39	22.39
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.5	0.27	0.27

MAX_MEAN: 0.818 MAX_MED: 0.864 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: C.I. Acid Orange 7

CHID: 38881 CASRN: 633-96-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091011

M4ID: 30005279

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	2.39	2.03	1.05
sd:	0.679	0.246	0.267

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	2.39	2.03	1.05	3.92	5.37
sd:	0.678	0.246	0.267	2160	7120

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	70.78	8.56	12.56
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.82	0.23	0.23

MAX_MEAN: 1.69 MAX_MED: 1.69 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Basic Blue 7

CHID: 38888 CASRN: 2390-60-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K11

M4ID: 30005375

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.09	1.67	1.66
sd:	0.485	0.0815	0.385

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.56	1.72	1.66	2.36	15.5
sd:	0.892	0.108	0.336	0.0158	8.09

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	128.12	55.84	56.24
PROB:	0	0.55	0.45
RMSE:	2.49	0.68	0.66

MAX_MEAN: 4.44 MAX_MED: 4.35 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 10

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Forskolin

CHID: 40484 CASRN: 66575-29-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J23

M4ID: 30005387

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.76	1.58	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.76	1.57	0.304	3.51	7.41
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	23.52	-3.37	0.64
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.35	0.18	0.18

MAX_MEAN: 0.592 MAX_MED: 0.606 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Octyl gallate
 CHID: 40713 CASRN: 1034-01-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091K19
 M4ID: 30005367

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	5.22	2.14	3.59
sd:	1.27	0.0862	1.13

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	5.22	2.14	3.59	3.54	7.97
sd:	1.28	0.0867	1.14	7700	49500

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	88.11	32.48	36.48
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	1.33	0.38	0.38

MAX_MEAN: 3.79 MAX_MED: 4.15 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Morin hydrate

CHID: 40776 CASRN: 654055-01-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091C19

M4ID: 30005559

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.987	1.95	3.33
sd:	0.137	0.0508	1.59

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.2	2	3.04	2.46	5.02
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	33.59	-12.48	-8.53
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.41	0.17	0.17

MAX_MEAN: 0.924 MAX_MED: 0.931 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1,4-Diaminoanthraquinone

CHID: 41252 CASRN: 128-95-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N07

M4ID: 30005307

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.81	2.4	0.681
sd:	3.65	2.34	0.534

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.66	2.3	0.704	4.05	4.01
sd:	3.01	2.09	0.546	1570	3610

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	52.16	24.76	28.77
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.56	0.32	0.32

MAX_MEAN: 0.87 MAX_MED: 0.82 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1-Monolaurin

CHID: 41275 CASRN: 142-18-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L23

M4ID: 30005339

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.553	-1.07	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.526	-1.48	0.3	3.83	7.37
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	43.22	-13.96	-10
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.45	0.17	0.16

MAX_MEAN: 0.656 MAX_MED: 0.665 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: C.I. Acid Violet 12, disodium salt

CHID: 41715 CASRN: 6625-46-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078K14

M4ID: 30005756

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.995	2.16	2.41
sd:	1.16	0.511	2.37

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.995	2.16	2.41	4.1	5.75
sd:	1.16	0.511	2.37	146000	472000

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	27.81	15.32	19.32
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.36	0.25	0.25

MAX_MEAN: 0.702 MAX_MED: 0.617 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1-Dodecyl-2-pyrrolidinone

CHID: 42206 CASRN: 2687-96-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078M11

M4ID: 30005711

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.99	2.27	1.1
sd:	1.16	0.448	0.42

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.99	2.27	1.1	3.8	5.06
sd:	1.16	0.448	0.42	1190	3960

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	46.88	0.67	4.67
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.53	0.22	0.22

MAX_MEAN: 1.2 MAX_MED: 1.07 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Acid Red 337

CHID: 44713 CASRN: 67786-14-5

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L07

M4ID: 30005355

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.85	1.93	0.722
sd:	0.868	0.607	0.283

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.85	1.93	0.722	3.84	5.32
sd:	0.868	0.607	0.283	1910	6590

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	70.24	23.74	27.74
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.73	0.3	0.3

MAX_MEAN: 1.24 MAX_MED: 1.29 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 5HPP-33
 CHID: 46970 CASRN: 105624-86-0
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078N02
 M4ID: 30005696

HILL MODEL (in red):
 tp ga gw
 val: 0.801 2.15 2.27
 sd: 0.574 0.33 1.42

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):
 tp ga gw la lw
 val: 0.801 2.15 2.27 3.98 3.91
 sd: 0.574 0.33 1.42 858 2050

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	8.01	-12.56	-8.56
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.26	0.16	0.16

MAX_MEAN: 0.563 MAX_MED: 0.528 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: CI-959

CHID: 47268 CASRN: 104795-68-8

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091J09

M4ID: 30005401

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.919	1.87	0.682
sd:	0.385	0.566	0.243

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.919	1.87	0.682	3.12	10.2
sd:	0.385	0.566	0.243	797	9920

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	28.57	-15.39	-11.39
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.37	0.16	0.16

MAX_MEAN: 0.658 MAX_MED: 0.722 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: SAR 150640

CHID: 47389 CASRN: 433212-21-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091M17

M4ID: 30005321

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.64	2.21	1.47
sd:	2.24	0.844	1.33

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.64	2.19	1.59	2.44	8.46
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	37.11	-4.62	-0.65
PROB:	0	0.88	0.12
RMSE:	0.45	0.2	0.2

MAX_MEAN: 1.03 MAX_MED: 0.893 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: FR167356
 CHID: 48174 CASRN: 174185-16-1
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091G05
 M4ID: 30005477

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.92	2.46	0.52
sd:	0.704	1.02	0.177

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.84	2.3	0.546	4.27	4.08
sd:	1.37	2.06	0.175	1060	2200

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	13.21	-21.66	-17.46
PROB:	0	0.89	0.11
RMSE:	0.29	0.15	0.15

MAX_MEAN: 0.606 MAX_MED: 0.541 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 42 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Nitrofurazone

CHID: 20944 CASRN: 59-87-0

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078005

M4ID: 30005669

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.68	1.97	8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.5	1.99	8	2.4	6.2
sd:	0.787	0.0217	5.99	0.0166	4.53

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	91.74	3.92	2.1
PROB:	0	0.29	0.71
RMSE:	1.4	0.23	0.2

MAX_MEAN: 3.62 MAX_MED: 3.6 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Phenylmercuric acetate

CHID: 21150 CASRN: 62-38-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091E09

M4ID: 30005521

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.92	1.81	8
sd:	0.107	0.0117	1.1

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.11	1.82	8	2.36	15.5
sd:	0.174	0.0117	1.15	0.0124	4.4

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	126.82	7.42	6.86
PROB:	0	0.43	0.57
RMSE:	2.03	0.22	0.21

MAX_MEAN: 3.84 MAX_MED: 3.84 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Dichlorophen
 CHID: 21824 CASRN: 97-23-4
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0091N13
 M4ID: 30005301

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.69	1.95	8
sd:	0.218	0.0128	2.6

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.74	1.98	8	2.35	9.87
sd:	0.55	0.0142	1.59	0.0145	4.57

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	105.88	41.17	40.99
PROB:	0	0.48	0.52
RMSE:	1.52	0.41	0.39

MAX_MEAN: 3.57 MAX_MED: 3.42 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2,4-Di-tert-pentylphenol

CHID: 26974 CASRN: 120-95-6

SPID(S): EPAPLT0091L16

M4ID: 30005346

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.65	1.95	8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.39	1.96	8	2.37	8.64
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	104.52	47.3	44.78
PROB:	0	0.22	0.78
RMSE:	1.56	0.45	0.41

MAX_MEAN: 3.46 MAX_MED: 3.46 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 1-Hydroxypyrene

CHID: 38298 CASRN: 5315-79-7

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078H20

M4ID: 30005822

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	1.1	1.88	8
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.4	1.93	7.98	2.34	9.65
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	45.7	-1.99	-3.95
PROB:	0	0.27	0.73
RMSE:	0.53	0.2	0.18

MAX_MEAN: 1.15 MAX_MED: 1.17 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 9-Phenanthroline
 CHID: 47592 CASRN: 484-17-3
 SPID(S): EPAPLT0078L04
 M4ID: 30005742

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.41	1.14	8
sd:	0.103	0.0372	1.97

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	4.36	1.2	6.97	2.81	0.662
sd:	2.51	0.0491	1.9	0.304	1.29

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	143.05	29.51	23.26
PROB:	0	0.04	0.96
RMSE:	2.4	0.33	0.29

MAX_MEAN: 3.75 MAX_MED: 3.68 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 50 ACTP: 1

FLAGS:

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: 2,4-Di-tert-butylphenol

CHID: 26602 CASRN: 96-76-4

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078C24

M4ID: 30005938

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	4.93e-11	1.45	1.58
sd:	7.22e-07	3820	72300

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	1.19	2.27	8	4.29	3.29
sd:	1.69	0.194	6.7	1660	2770

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	17.9	23.9	10.81
PROB:	0.03	0	0.97
RMSE:	0.32	0.32	0.22

MAX_MEAN: 0.748 MAX_MED: 0.756 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 0.97

FLAGS: 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Limonene

CHID: 29612 CASRN: 138-86-3

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I23

M4ID: 30005795

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	0.237	2.64	0.3
sd:	NaN	NaN	NaN

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.587	2.26	8	3.79	3.76
sd:	1.83	0.45	22.4	2040	5160

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-12.1	-9.84	-18.83
PROB:	0.03	0.01	0.96
RMSE:	0.19	0.17	0.14

MAX_MEAN: 0.404 MAX_MED: 0.425 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 0.97

FLAGS: 11; 6

ASSAY: AEID2489 (NCCT_AIME_384WELL_CTox_Active_dn)

NAME: Codlelure

CHID: 35288 CASRN: 33956-49-9

SPID(S): EPAPLT0078I01

M4ID: 30005817

HILL MODEL (in red):

	tp	ga	gw
val:	3.39e-11	1.62	1.3
sd:	1.41e-06	5500	58400

GAIN-LOSS MODEL (in blue):

	tp	ga	gw	la	lw
val:	0.851	2.27	8	4.3	3.08
sd:	0.7	0.108	5.87	784	1220

	CNST	HILL	GNLS
AIC:	-15.05	-9.05	-31.88
PROB:	0	0	1
RMSE:	0.21	0.21	0.12

MAX_MEAN: 0.561 MAX_MED: 0.535 BMAD: 0.14

COFF: 0.421 HIT-CALL: 1 FITC: 51 ACTP: 1

FLAGS: 6